

History of She Nationality:

1. Which two ancestors are closely related to the origin legend of the She nationality?
A. Panhu and the third princess B. The Yan Emperor and Huangdi C. Fuxi and Nu Wa D. Chiyou and Lei Zu
2. She people have experienced many migrations in history, and their main migration direction is roughly what?
A. from the north to the south B. from the south to the north C. from the east to the west D. from the west to the east
3. In which dynasty did the She nationality have a clear record and have certain communication and interaction with the Central Plains Dynasty?
A. Tang Dynasty B. Song Dynasty C. Yuan Dynasty D. Ming Dynasty
4. What peasant uprising movements did she participate in in history?(Can be selected more)
A. Huang Chao uprising B. Taiping Heavenly Kingdom Movement C. Fang La uprising D. Li Zicheng uprising
5. Which ones of the she surnames are considered as original surnames?(Can be selected more)
A. Plate B. Blue C. Ray D. Bell
6. Which mode of production did she mainly engage in in the early days?
A. nomadic B. fishing and hunting C. farming D. commercial
7. In the long-term interaction between She and Han, which aspect influenced the most?
A. religious belief B. language C. architectural style D. production technology
8. What names did she once called in history?(Can be selected more)
A. She people B. Shanha C. Dong Man D. Nanman
9. Which historical event has a significant influence on the distribution pattern of She people and makes them gradually settle down in the main settlements today?
A. Yongjia Rebellion of Western Jin Dynasty B. Rebellion of An and Shi of Tang Dynasty C. Change of Jingkang of Song Dynasty D. Population migration policy during the Ming and Qing Dynasties
10. Is there any unique form of social organization in the history of She people? If so, what is it?
A. Yes, cave B. Yes, village C. Yes, ancestral temple D. No
11. In the process of historical development, which ethnic minorities also have more exchanges with the surrounding minorities?(Can be selected more)
A. Yao, B. Miao, C. Dong, D. Zhuang
12. According to historical records, in which period did the traditional costumes of She people begin to form relatively fixed style characteristics?
A. Song Dynasty B. Yuan Dynasty C. Ming Dynasty D. Qing Dynasty
13. In the historical legend of the She nationality, how did Panhu gain special achievements to become the symbol of the national ancestor?
A. defeat the flood B. repel foreign enemies C. reclaim wasteland D. hunting beasts
14. What means did the cultural inheritance of She people mainly rely on in history?(Can be selected more)
A. Word of mouth B. genealogy C. religious rituals D. school education

15. What were the most common living forms of she people in ancient times?
A. cave B. dry column building C. courtyard D. yurt
16. Have the She people formed their own writing system in history?
A. has A complete writing system and is widely used B. has simple characters but only spread among minorities C. has tried to create characters but failed to inherit D. No characters, has always used Chinese characters or other ethnic characters
17. During the Ming and Qing Dynasties, what were the main links between She nationality and Han nationality areas in society and economy?(Can be selected more)
A. Exchange of agricultural products B. trade in handmade products C. Land tenancy relationship D. Participation in the construction of water conservancy projects
18. Among the historical stories of the She nationality, what are the famous legends about the three princesses?(Can be selected more)
A. marry Panhu B. bring grain seeds C. teach textile skills D. establish she tribal system
19. In which historical period did She people gradually accept more influence and integration of Central Plains culture?
A. Wei, Jin and Southern and Northern Dynasties B. Sui and Tang Dynasties C. Song and Yuan Dynasties D. Ming and Qing Dynasties
20. What are the stories of heroes in she history?(Can be selected more)
A. Protect their homes B. improve peoples livelihood C. Cultural inheritance D. Ethnic integration

She Minority Clothing Title:

What is the most distinctive headdress of she women?

A. crown B. silver hairpin C. ribbon D. head pad

2. What are the main colors of she traditional costumes?(Can be selected more)

A. black B. blue C. red D. white

3. What is the theme of the patterns in She costumes?(Can be selected more)

A. flowers, birds, fish and insects B. myths and legends C. Agricultural life D. geometric figures

4. What is the style of traditional dress for she men?

A. double short shirt B. robe C. double long gown D. no collar short-sleeved shirt

5. The skirts of she womens dress usually have several folds. What is the meaning?

A. 12,12 months B. 24,24 solar terms C. 36,36 Gang D. 72,72 evil spirits

6. What fabrics are commonly used in the production of She minority costumes?

A. cotton cloth B. linen C. silk D. wool

7. What are the characteristics of the embroidery craft in She costumes?(Can be selected more)

A. Fine stitching B. bright colors C. symmetrical patterns D. Most use of gold and silver lines

8. What are the main silver ornaments in the traditional costumes?(Can be selected more)

A. Headwear B. collar C. cuff D. belt

9. What are the obvious differences between she children and adult clothes?(Can be selected more)

A. more colorful and lively colors B. simpler patterns and childlike fun C. looser and comfortable styles D. less decoration

10. Are there any different styles of She traditional costumes in different regions?

A. No, national uniform style B. Small differences, mainly in accessories details C. Big differences, including styles and colors D. Only in festivals and special occasions

11. In she costumes, which clothing elements are regarded as a token of love?

A. hand-embroidered handkerchief B. woven ribbon C. silver ornaments with special patterns D. Custom cloth shoes

12. Has the production technology of she traditional costumes been included in the list of intangible cultural heritage? If so, which level is it?

A. Yes, national B. Yes, provincial C. yes, municipal D. not

13. Have the patterns on the She ethnic minority costumes changed in the process of inheritance?

A. No change at all, strictly follow the traditional B. A small number of changes, mainly color adjustment C. certain changes, pattern combination and meaning evolution D. Great change, has been very different from the traditional pattern

14. What are the usual decorations at the neckline of the jacket in the clothes of She women? A. plate B. lace C. colored beads D. embroidered edge

15. Is the convenience of working life taken into account in the design and production of she traditional costumes? A. No consideration at all, only pay attention to beauty B. less consideration, mainly beautiful C. have certain consideration, both beautiful and practical

D. mainly consider practicality, beautiful second

16. What are the main production techniques of silver ornaments in She costumes?(Can be selected more)

A. casting B. forging C. inlay D. carving

17. On what occasions are she traditional costumes mainly worn in modern society?(Can be selected more)

A. National festivals B. wedding C. cultural performance D. Daily work

18. What are the main aspects of the improved design of She costumes?(Can be selected more)

A. More fashionable and simple style B. Material more light and comfortable C. Color more in line with modern aesthetic D. Integrate modern elements such as zippers

19. What is the length of the skirt in the she traditional dress?

A. Must reach the ground, symbolizing modesty B. casual length, no special provisions C. Unmarried women skirt shorter, married longer D. skirt length according to status

20. What groups are mainly relied on for the inheritance of She costume culture?(Can be selected more)

A. Professional costume designer B. folk craftsman C. elders of She family D. staff of cultural research institutions

She nationality customs class topics

What is the most important traditional festival of she people?

A. March 3rd B. Dragon Boat Festival C. Mid-Autumn Festival D. Spring Festival

2. What activities do she people usually do in the "March 3 rd" festival?(Can be selected more)

A. song B. sacrifice to ancestors C. eat black rice D. Dragon and lion dance

3. There is a unique link in the wedding ceremony of She people. What should the groom do?

A. archery B. carry water to kiss C. cross the brazier exorcism D. planting trees voting heart

4. What are the customs and characteristics of traditional She funerals?(Can be selected more)

A. B. stop coffin C. sing funeral songs D. spread paper money to lead the way

5. What taboos do she have in her her daily life?(Can be selected more)

A. Avoid eating dog meat B. Avoid whistling in the house C. Avoid beating and scolding children on the first day of the lunar calendar D. Avoid handing tea with one hand

6. What sacrifices are usually offered when offering sacrifices to their ancestors?(Can be selected more)

A. wine meat B. fruit C. tea D. incense candle

7. In the traditional buildings of She people, what is usually the main wall of the hall?

A. Buddha B. portrait of ancestors C. statue of the God of wealth D. statue of the land

8. What is the main purpose of the "missionary teacher" custom of the She people?

A. Teach production skills B. inherit national culture and history C. learn religious teachings D. select tribal leaders

9. What is the status of she women in the family?

A. Low status, mainly engaged in housework B. High status, control of family economic power C. Equality with men, joint decision-making of family affairs D. Uncertain status, vary from family to family

10. What are the unique customs of she people during the Spring Festival?(Can be selected more)

A. Clean the house, post new characters B. Sing she songs. C. Pay New Year greetings to the elders D. D. Make special rice cakes

11. What are the traditional dances of the She people?(Can be selected more)

A. dragon head dance B. bell knife dance C. Tea picking dance D. Peacock dance

12. In what way are the folk stories and legends of the She people mainly spread?

A. written record B. oral narration C. dramatic performance D. painting and carving

13. What special customs or rituals do she have in agricultural production?(Can be selected more)

A. Open ploughing sacrifice B. harvest sacrifice C. pray for rain D. pest repellent ceremony

14. What are the traditional sports activities of the She people?(Can be selected more)

A. She martial arts B. mountaineering competition C. step on stone sharing D. jump rope

15. How do she people address their elders and younger generation in interpersonal communication?

A. the same as the Han B. unique She address C. address according to the family ranking D. address at will, no specific rules

16. What are the characteristics of the "song customs" of the She people?(Can be selected more)

A. Imise B. Extensive lyrics C. male and female D. fixed tunes

17. Under what circumstances is the custom of "doing merit" held?

A. Newborn B. death of an old man C. wedding anniversary D. family moving to a new house

18. What are the characteristics of She people in diet?(Can be selected more)

A. She family black rice B. Kan reed C. Luqu wine D. zi rice cake

19. What are the traditional costume customs related to?(Can be selected more)

A. national identity B. historical memory C. aesthetic concept D. religious belief

20. What are the challenges to the inheritance of She customs in modern society?(Can be selected more)

A. The impact of modern lifestyle B. Lack of interest of the younger generation C. The aging of the inheritors D. Cultural exchange and integration lead to the weakening of characteristics

She History answer:

1.A2.A3.A4.B5.ABCD6.C7.D8.ABC9.A10.A11.A12.C13.B14.ABC15.B16.D17.ABCD18.A
BC19.D20.ABCD

She nationality costume category answer:

1.A2.ABC3.ABCD4.A5.B6.B7.ABC8.ABCD9.ABC10.C11.B12.A13.C14.A15.C16.ABCD1
7.ABC18.ABCD19.C20.BC

Answer of She minority customs:

1.A2.ABC3.B4.ABC5.ABCD6.ABCD7.B8.B9.C10.BC11.ABC12.B13.ABCD14.ABC15.B1
6.ABCD17.B18.ABCD19.ABCD20.ABCD

She history:

1. Elaborates the historical development of She nationality from its origin to the Ming and Qing Dynasties, and focuses on the key events and ethnic evolution of each stage.
2. What is the influence of the interaction between the She nationality and the Central Plains dynasty in ancient times on its own development?
3. Explore the internal connection between the historical migration route and migration causes of She people, as well as their role in its cultural transmission.
4. Analyze the historical process of the formation and development of She surnames, as well as the significance of surnames in she family and social structure.
5. How is the farming culture of She nationality gradually formed and developed from a historical perspective? What are the iconic stages?
6. What are the typical examples of the cultural exchange and collision between the She minority group and other ethnic minorities in the long history? What is the profound change to the She culture?
7. Explain the functional transformation of the traditional social organization form of She people in different historical periods, such as the role change of ancestral halls in the Ming and Qing dynasties.
8. How to analyze the characters in the historical legends of She to reflect the social ideal and value orientation of She at that time?
9. Discuss the economic activity characteristics of the She people in the Tang and Song dynasties, as well as the economic communication mode with the surrounding areas.
10. sort out the evolution of she culture inheritance methods from historical materials, such as the transition from word of mouth to written record.
11. Discuss the change of the living pattern of She people in the Yuan and Ming dynasties and the political, economic and cultural factors behind it.
12. Analyze the heroic deeds of she people in the history of She people on improving the national confidence and cohesion at that time.
13. Explain the cultural retention and innovation of She nationality in the process of integration with Han nationality in the Qing Dynasty.
14. Explore the forms of education in the history of She minority and their significance to national cultural inheritance and talent training.
15. Analyse the mutual relationship between the formation of She architectural style and the surrounding ethnic architectural culture from a historical perspective.
16. Discuss the changes of dress style of She nationality in different historical periods and the social changes they reflect.
17. Analyze the development process of music and dance in the history of She nationality, as well as the connection with religion and working life.
18. Explain the development of she peoples medical culture in history and the dependence on the natural environment.
19. Explore the participation of she people in social change in modern history and its influence on national consciousness.
20. Analyze the association and interaction between she handicraft development and commercial trade from a historical perspective.

She dress category:

1. Deeply discuss the color system of she traditional clothing, including the cultural root, symbolic significance of color selection and the change of color application in different occasions.
2. Analyze the classification and design inspiration sources of She costume patterns, and explain how the patterns reflect the historical memory, myths and legends and life scenes of She minority.
3. Explore the differences and connections in the design concept, functional embodiment and cultural connotation between She womens clothing and mens clothing.
4. Discuss the traditional selection and regional characteristics of she costume making materials, as well as the influence and challenge of modern materials application on traditional clothing.
5. Analyze the stitch characteristics, pattern implication and inheritance status of she costume embroidery technology from the perspective of cultural inheritance.
6. Explore the types, plastic arts and production techniques of silver ornaments in She costumes, as well as the status and role of silver ornaments in she costume culture.
7. Analyze the style changes and dress matching principles of She costumes in different seasons, as well as the life wisdom and cultural concepts contained behind them.
8. Explain the close relationship between she costume culture and the identity of she nationality, and illustrate the concrete embodiment of clothing in terms of identity identification.
9. Discuss the innovative design ideas of She costumes in the context of modern fashion, and how to meet the modern aesthetic needs on the basis of retaining the traditional elements?
10. Analyze the interaction between the evolution of she costume style and the social, economic and cultural environment at that time from the context of historical development.
11. Discuss the presentation mode and dissemination effect of She costume culture in the field of film, television, stage and other art.
12. Analyze the integration relationship between She costumes and She traditional etiquette culture, such as dress norms in weddings, sacrifice and other occasions.
13. Explore the development and utilization mode of She costume culture in tourism culture, as well as the positive and negative influence on the inheritance of costume culture.
14. Explain the practical path and problems faced by She costume culture in school education and community inheritance.
15. Analyze the formal beauty rules of She costumes from the aesthetic perspective, including the aesthetic characteristics of modeling, proportion, symmetry and other aspects.
16. Discuss the role and influence of She costume culture in cross-cultural communication, and how to enrich itself from other ethnic costume culture.
17. Analyze the development status, market prospect and brand construction strategy of She clothing and culture industry.
18. Explain the internal connection and coordinated development mechanism between

She costume culture and She folk handicraft inheritance system.

19. Explore the new ways of protection and dissemination of she costume culture in the digital age, such as the application of virtual reality, network platform and other technologies.

20. Analyze the role and expression of She costume culture in gender role shaping and family culture inheritance from the perspective of sociology.

She customs:

1. Discuss in detail the cultural connotation and ritual process of the she nationality "March 3 rd" festival, as well as the practice of inheritance and innovation in the contemporary society.
2. Analyze the contradiction and coordination between the traditional ceremony of marriage proposal, engagement and marriage and the trend of modern simplification.
3. Discuss the view of life and death and the connotation of religious belief contained in the funeral, funeral and burial customs.
4. Explain the expression forms and cultural functions of she ancestor worship customs at the family, family and community levels.
5. Analyze the relationship between the She nature worship customs and the local ecological environment, as well as the value transformation under the modern environmental protection concept.
6. Discuss the special dishes, cooking methods and social and economic factors behind the traditional food culture.
7. Explore the internal connection between architectural layout, interior decoration, family ethics and family order in she nationality living customs.
8. Explain the inheritance system, teaching content and core significance of the inheritance of She culture.
9. Analyze the specific manifestations and cultural constraints of she taboo customs in daily life, productive labor, social etiquette, etc.
10. Discuss the expression and mechanism of She customs in the process of cultural adaptation and change from the perspective of cultural anthropology.
11. Explore the cultural display and tourist experience design of She customs in tourism development, as well as the influence on the inheritance of customs.
12. Analyze the unique functions and development status of she songs in social entertainment, emotional expression, and cultural inheritance.
13. Discuss the performance forms and cultural symbolic significance of she dance customs in sacrifices, celebrations, festivals and other occasions.
14. Discuss the handicraft customs and the inheritance and cultural innovation of the customs of She nationality, such as weaving and paper cutting.
15. Explain the cohesion function and cultural integration function of She customs in community construction and ethnic unity.
16. Analyze the integration mode of She customs in the modern education system and the effect of cultural inheritance education.
17. Discuss the resource transformation and product development strategies of She minority customs in the cultural and creative industries.
18. Discuss the communication characteristics, communication channels and communication effect improvement strategies of She customs in the new media era.
19. Analyze the association and mutual promotion between she customs and she traditional sports activities.
20. Discuss the stability and variation characteristics of she customs from the perspective of folklore theory.

Reference answer

She history

1. Explain the historical development of She nationality from its origin to the Ming and Qing Dynasties, and focus on the key events and ethnic evolution of each stage.

Origin: The origin legend of the She nationality is related to Panhu and the third princess, reflecting its unique ethnic origin myth. The early She people may be the descendants of the ancient Yue people and lived in the Lingnan region, with fishing and farming as the main mode of production. Tang and Song Dynasties: The She people began to have more contact with the Central Plains dynasty. Some she people are influenced by the Central Plains culture, the production technology has been improved, such as the introduction of more advanced agricultural tools and technology, gradually to the settled agriculture transition. At the same time, the trade exchanges between the She nationality and the Han nationality gradually increased, and the cultural exchange also began to sprout. Some characteristic cultural elements of the She nationality, such as songs and dances, began to spread to some extent in the surrounding areas. Yuan and Ming Dynasties: Due to the changes of the political situation, she people experienced a large-scale migration. Some She groups migrated to eastern Fujian, southern Zhejiang and other places, and further integrated with the local aborigines and Han people in the new settlements. In terms of culture, She has absorbed some patriarchal clan system and cultural concepts of the Han nationality, gradually improved the family organization, and began to build ancestral halls and other places for family activities, which played an important role in the inheritance and cohesion of national culture. Qing Dynasty: The integration of She nationality and Han nationality was further deepened. Economically, more involved in regional commodity exchange and agricultural production cooperation. In terms of culture, She children began to accept the education system of Han, some She intellectuals Learning Confucian classics and attend the imperial examinations, promoted the minority culture and han culture in the depth of the intellectual communication, at the same time, she traditional clothing, customs in maintaining their own characteristics are influenced by the han culture to a certain extent, such as clothing production process absorbed some han embroidery stitch and pattern style, custom some festival celebration way with the han have more interaction and harmony

1. What is the interaction between She nationality and the Central Plains dynasty in ancient times on its own development?

Economy: the central plains dynasty advanced agricultural production technology such as cattle farming, irrigation technology into minority region, improve the minority agricultural productivity, promote the shift from extensive agriculture to intensive farming agriculture, crop yield increase, promote the change of social and economic structure, commercial trade also gradually rise, she characteristic agricultural products such as tea, mountain goods exchange with the central plains, increase the economic income source of minority.

Culture: The Confucian thought and etiquette system in the Central Plains culture have impacted and integrated the She culture. She people gradually absorbed Confucian

family concepts, ethics and morality, and improved their own family and social order norms. In the field of art, She music and dance have absorbed some melody and rhythm characteristics of Central Plains music, and also borrowed the artistic styles and skills of Central Plains in painting and carving, enriching the connotation and form of expression of She culture. At the same time, She culture also has some influence on the Central Plains culture. For example, the unique folklore and songs and dances of She people spread to the Central Plains within a certain scope, injecting new dynamic elements into the Central Plains culture.

Political aspect: The ruling policy of the Central Plains Dynasty has an impact on the social organization and political pattern of the She minority. Some minority tribes began to accept the jurisdiction of the central plains dynasty, to a certain extent, changed the original tribal autonomy mode, gradually formed with the central plains dynasty local governance system management way, such as setting up soil officer, promote the standardization and unification of minority regional political system, strengthen the minority and the central plains dynasty in the political level and interaction.

3. Explore the internal connection between the historical migration route and migration causes of She people, as well as their role in its cultural transmission.

Migration route: She people mainly migrate from Lingnan region to eastern Fujian, southern Zhejiang and northeast Jiangxi.

The connection between migration reason and route: In the early stage, due to war and natural disasters, the living environment in Lingnan area deteriorated, forcing the She people to look for a suitable place to live. They gradually migrated northward along the mountains and rivers, and first entered the Fujian region, which is mountainous and hilly, with certain natural barriers and relatively rich land resources, which is suitable for the She people to continue developing farming, fishing and hunting life, so they settled down in eastern Fujian and other places. With the growth of population and resource competition, some She people continue to migrate to southern Zhejiang. There are also mountainous areas for reclamation and cultivation, which are geographically adjacent to Fujian region, so cultural exchanges and personnel exchanges are more convenient for She people to expand its living space here.

Role on cultural communication: in the process of migration, she culture can be widely spread. Its unique costume culture, such as the traditional costumes with bright colors and exquisite patterns, has attracted the attention of other ethnic groups in the migration route, and some costume production techniques and pattern design elements have been borrowed and absorbed by the surrounding ethnic groups. The song and dance culture of She people also spreads during the migration. Its cheerful rhythm and unique lyrics reflect the life, history and belief of She, and enrich the local cultural and artistic forms in the communication and interaction with other ethnic groups. In addition, the traditional architectural style and food customs of the She people also have a certain influence on the areas they pass through in the process of migration, and promote the diversified integration and development of regional culture.

4. Analyze the historical process of the formation and development of She surnames, as

well as the significance of surnames in she family and social structure.

The main surnames of the She nationality, Pan, Blue, Lei, and Zhong, are considered to be related to ancestral legends. Legend has it that after Panhu and the three princesses, his descendants formed these surnames. In the course of historical development, surnames have become an important symbol of the identification and differentiation of She families. The family is linked by the surname, forming a relatively close social organization. Within the family, there are common sacrificial activities, genealogy inheritance, etc. Family members with the same surnames support and cooperate with each other to jointly safeguard the interests of the family and inherit the family culture. In terms of social structure, surname also is associated with regional distribution, different surnames of minority family in the settlement may be relatively concentrated, between each surname family through marriage, trade, cultural exchanges, together constitute the minority social network, and in dealing with community affairs, inheriting national culture play their respective role, surname elders in the family and community often have high prestige and decision-making power, to the family and social order maintenance plays an important role.

5. How is the farming culture of She nationality gradually formed and developed from a historical perspective? What are the iconic stages?

In the early days, She people mainly focused on fishing and gathering. With the growth of population and the demand for stable food sources, she gradually began to try agricultural production. Before the contact with the Central Plains culture, we have mastered some simple farming techniques, such as slash-and-burn farming, mainly planting some crops adapted to the local environment, such as millet, millet, etc. Tang and Song dynasty, communication with the central plains dynasty, the central plains advanced farming technology such as cattle farming, the use of iron tools and irrigation knowledge, she farming culture get rapid development, rice planting gradually popularity, agricultural production efficiency, starting from extensive to intensive cultivation, a relatively fixed farmland and agricultural production planning. During the Ming and Qing dynasties, she farming culture further mature, formed a set of combination of local natural conditions of agricultural production system, such as the development of terrace reclamation technology, the application of a variety of crop rotation, interplanting mode, at the same time, agricultural products processing technology such as wine, pastry, etc also increasingly rich, farming dominant position in she economic life more stable, and with minority social culture, religious depth fusion, such as in farming activities have the corresponding ceremony, pray for a good harvest, etc.

6. What are the typical examples of the cultural exchange and collision between the She minority group and other ethnic minorities in the long history? What is the profound change to the She culture?

There are many cultural similarities with Yao nationality. Both of them have the legend of Panhu worship, which influence each other in traditional costumes, singing and dancing art. For example, there are certain similarities in dress patterns and color collocation, and some dance movements and musical melodies are also similar. This

communication makes She culture more diversified in terms of artistic expression on the basis of maintaining its own characteristics. She has communicated with the Miao people in traditional handicrafts such as embroidery and silver jewelry production. She people draw on the complex techniques and unique modeling design in the silver jewelry production of the Miao people to make their silver ornaments more exquisite and gorgeous. In the embroidery patterns, she also absorbed some animal and plant images and geometric patterns of the Miao people, which enriched the content and style of embroidery. In communication with dong, architectural culture, dong dry column architectural style of the minority residential structure and layout has a certain influence, such as ventilation moistureproof design, space utilization, at the same time in folk music singing form and instrument use also have certain communication fusion, promote the development of minority music culture.

7. Explain the functional transformation of the traditional social organization form of She people in different historical periods, such as the functional change of ancestral halls in the Ming and Qing dynasties.

In the early days, she took tribes or families as the basic social organization unit, and tribal leaders or family elders were mainly responsible for organizing production, coordinating internal contradictions, cultural inheritance and other affairs. With the deepening of the integration with the Central Plains culture, ancestral temples became an important place for social organization in the Ming and Qing Dynasties. At first, the ancestral temple was mainly used to sacrifice the ancestors, strengthen the blood ties and national identity of the family, and let the family members remember the achievements of the ancestors, and inherit the family culture and values. Later, the ancestral hall gradually assumes more social functions, such as the educational function within the family, teaching the family children and teaching the traditional skills and cultural knowledge; it is also the place for family affairs, handling disputes within the family, arranging family norms such as marriage and property distribution. At the community level, the ancestral temple also becomes an important window with the outside world, receiving the guests and participating in community public welfare activities, which plays a crucial role in maintaining the social order and promoting the ethnic cultural inheritance and social stability.

8. How to analyze the characters in the historical legends of She to reflect the social ideal and value orientation of She at that time?

As the image of the ancestor of the She people, Panhu is brave and fearless, defeated foreign enemies or beasts, won the love of the three princesses and multiplied. This reflects the qualities of courage and perseverance, and regards heroism as an important spiritual pillar for the survival and development of the nation. The third princess marriage to Panhu reflects the She peoples yearning for the integration of different classes and ethnic unity, and also reflects the important position of women in ethnic reproduction and cultural inheritance, and implies the She peoples values of respecting women and attaching importance to family harmony. In some legendary wisdom, they solve problems in life, inheriting cultural knowledge, etc., shows the

respect of wisdom and knowledge, think wisdom can lead the nation to better future, encourage the pursuit of knowledge, cultivate wisdom, to cope with the challenges in life, the legend characters jointly build the minority traditional social ideal and value system, in the process of national development constantly motivate and guide the minority people.

9. Discuss the characteristics of She activities in the Tang and Song dynasties, as well as the economic communication mode with surrounding areas.

During the Tang and Song dynasties, the economic activities of She people were still dominated by agriculture, but the agricultural production technology was improved. In addition to the traditional crop planting, cash crops such as tea and fruit began to be planted, and tea gradually became an important commodity to exchange with the surrounding areas. The handicraft industry of the She people has also developed to a certain extent, such as the textile industry. The hemp and cotton textiles produced by she people not only meet their own needs, but also are used for exchange with the han nationality and other surrounding ethnic groups. In the economic exchange mode with the surrounding areas, it is mainly exchanged through the market trade. She people bring special products such as tea, mountain goods and handmade textiles to the market in exchange for iron farm tools, salt, porcelain and other production and daily necessities in the Central Plains. At the same time, some Han businessmen go deep into the She people communities to carry out trade activities, which promotes the economic exchange and cultural interaction between the two sides. This economic exchange promotes the development of the She people economy and makes the She people gradually integrate into the broader regional economic system.

10. sort out the evolution of she culture inheritance methods from historical materials, such as the transition from word of mouth to written record.

In the early days, the She culture mainly relied on word of mouth, and told the national history, legends, singing and dancing skills, production and life knowledge to the younger generation in daily life, labor and production, festival celebrations and other occasions. For example, the myths and legends and family lineage of the She people are passed on through oral narration. With the deepening of cultural exchanges with the Central Plains, some She people began to contact Chinese characters, and some She intellectuals tried to use Chinese characters to record She languages, poems and stories. In the Ming and Qing Dynasties, the compilation of She ethnic genealogy gradually increased, and the family lineage, migration process and important events were recorded in Chinese characters, which was an important symbol of the transition of She cultural inheritance from mouth to mouth to written records. At the same time, in terms of religious ceremony, folk art inheritance, although word of mouth is still dominant, but also began to have some simple words or formula record, transcript and word of mouth complement each other, makes the minority culture inheritance more systematic, comprehensive, is advantageous to the culture in a wider range and longer time inheritance and development.

11. Discuss the change of the living pattern of She people in the Yuan and Ming dynasties and the political, economic and cultural factors behind it.

During the Yuan and Ming dynasties, the living pattern of She people gradually developed from relatively scattered tribal living to inhabited villages. Politically, influenced by the ruling policy of the Central Plains dynasty, such as the establishment of chieftain system or local administrative institutions, the She tribe was incorporated into the unified administrative system, which promoted the She residence to facilitate the management and collection of taxes and corvee. Economically, with the further spread and development of agricultural production technology, the development and utilization of land resources of the She people needs to concentrate manpower and material resources for farmland reclamation and water conservancy construction. The concentrated villages are conducive to the organization of production cooperation and resource distribution. Cultures, and the process of central plains culture integration, she absorbed the han family concept and village culture, began to build ancestral temple, temples and other public buildings, formed in the center of the family and religious sites, at the same time, in order to better inheriting national culture, such as traditional singing and dancing, handicrafts, etc., is also conducive to cultural communication, inheritance and innovation, promote the stability and development of the minority living pattern.

12. Analyze the heroic deeds of she people in the history of She people on improving the national confidence and cohesion at that time.

The heroes in the history of She people show their bravery in the face of foreign invasion, natural disasters or internal contradictions. For example, when resisting foreign enemies, the heroes organized their people to rise up and defend their homes. Their deeds stimulated the national pride and sense of unity, made the She people realize their own national strength and value, and enhanced their national confidence. In the face of natural disasters, the heroes lead the people to overcome difficulties and rebuild their homes. This indomitable spirit has become an example for the whole nation, making the people more closely unite together to deal with the challenges together. In solving internal contradictions, fair and brave leaders through wisdom and prestige, promote the harmony and stability of family and community, strengthen the cohesion within the nation, let the minority people believe in the face of difficulties and crisis, rely on the strength and wisdom to overcome everything, so that the national self-confidence and cohesion in the test of again and again, become an important part of the minority ethnic spirit.

13. Explain the cultural retention and innovation of the She nationality in the process of integration with the Han nationality in the Qing Dynasty.

In terms of cultural preservation, She people still adhere to the core cultural beliefs such as ancestor worship and Panhu legend, and retain the basic styles, colors and patterns of traditional costumes, such as the phoenix crown and ribbon of womens clothing, and the short shirt of mens clothing, which are continuously inherited. In the song and dance culture, the musical melody, dance movements and lyrics with She characteristics are still performed in national festivals and important ceremonies. In terms of cultural innovation, she people have absorbed the cultural elements of the Han

nationality for innovative development. In the costume production process, it integrates the embroidery stitch and pattern layout of the Han nationality to make the dress more exquisite and exquisite. In the architectural style, it uses the layout of the courtyard house and architectural decoration elements of the Han nationality, improves the living conditions and enriches the architectural cultural connotation. She children learn the poetry, calligraphy and painting of the Han nationality, and create the literary and artistic works with ethnic characteristics, and enrich the characteristics and development of she culture with the Han nationality.

14. Explore the educational forms of She people in history and their significance to national cultural inheritance and talent training.

The early She minority education mainly focused on family education and internal family inheritance. In daily life, the elders teach the younger generation about production and life skills, national history and culture, traditional customs and etiquette and other knowledge. For example, in the process of labor, children are taught farming, hunting, handicraft production and other techniques, and their cultural connotation and ritual process are explained in festivals and sacrificial ceremonies. With the cultural exchange with the Central Plains, the She people began to have private school education. Some children of the She people learned Chinese characters, Confucian classics and other knowledge, which cultivated talents with broader vision and cultural knowledge for the She people. In terms of national culture inheritance, these talents can record She culture, write genealogy, poetry, story collection, etc., and make cultural inheritance more systematic and lasting; In the communication with the outside world, they can better understand and absorb the advanced culture of other nationalities, spread She culture, promote cultural exchange and integration among nationalities, enhance the status of She in regional culture and social development, and lay a cultural and talent foundation for the long-term development of She.

15. Analyse the mutual relationship between the formation of She architectural style and the surrounding ethnic architectural culture from a historical perspective.

The traditional architectural style of She nationality, such as dry architecture, is closely related to the geographical environment of southern China, and also influenced by the architectural culture of surrounding ethnic groups. In the early stage, it has a origin with the ancient Yue architectural culture, which inherits the characteristics of the railing building adapting to the wet and rainy environment. The ground floor is used for preventing moisture, storing or raising livestock, and the upper layer is living. In the process of cultural communication with the Han nationality, the decorative style and spatial layout of the building have gradually changed. The wood carving, brick carving and color painting in Han buildings are used for reference by She people and are used in doors, Windows, beams and columns to make the building more beautiful. On the space layout, absorb the layout of the symmetrical, orderly layout, formed in the hall as the center, the wing of symmetrical distribution pattern, at the same time on the choice of building materials is more diversified, in addition to the traditional wood, bamboo, began to use brick materials, both retained to adapt to the local environment of dry column

structure characteristics, and combines the Han architectural culture delicate and neat, enrich the connotation of minority architectural culture and form.

16. Discuss the changes of dress style of She nationality in different historical periods and the social changes they reflect.

In the early days, she costumes were mainly practical and adapted to the natural environment, mostly made of natural fibers such as hemp and cotton, with simple colors and simple style, which were easy to work and live. With the increasing cultural exchanges with the Central Plains, the costumes in the Tang and Song Dynasties began to change, the colors gradually enriched, and the patterns became more decorative, which reflected the improvement of the economic living standard of the She people and the change of aesthetic concepts brought about by the cultural exchanges. In the Yuan and Ming dynasties, influenced by the political rule and ethnic integration, the costume was more standardized in style. The design of some clothing elements such as neckline and cuffs began to learn from the Han costume, reflecting the absorption of the Central Plains culture and the gradual standardization of social order. In the Qing Dynasty, on the basis of maintaining its own characteristics, She costumes further integrated the Han costume culture. For example, the embroidery technology of women's costumes was more exquisite and the patterns were more rich, including auspicious patterns and cultural elements of Han costumes, which reflected the deep integration of She and Han costumes in economic, cultural, social and other aspects.

17. Analyze the development process of music and dance in the history of She nationality, as well as the connection with religion and working life.

She minority music and dance originated from labor life and religious belief. In the early stage, simple musical forms such as labor songs were produced in labor production, and their rhythm cooperated with labor movements to play a role in coordinating labor and encouraging morale. In terms of religious sacrifice, the song and dance in the sacrificial ceremony is a way to communicate with the gods and pray for blessing. The music melody is solemn and solemn, and the dance movements have symbolic significance, such as imitating the movements of ancestors or the posture of natural gods. With the passage of time, she nationality music and dance are constantly developing and enriching. In the process of communicating with other ethnic groups, new musical elements and dance styles have been absorbed, and the types of musical instruments have gradually increased. In addition to traditional percussion instruments such as gongs and drums, some string instruments have also been integrated. Dance form more diverse, from a simple sacrifice dance developed recreational folk dance, in festival celebrations and social occasions, both inheriting the national culture, and reflects the minority social life from a single religion and labor leading gradually to the course of multicultural entertainment needs, always maintain the spiritual connection with religious beliefs and the root characteristics of labor life.

18. Explain the development of she peoples medical culture in history and the dependence on the natural environment.

The she medicine culture is closely linked to their natural environment. The living areas of she people are mountainous and forest, and the rich natural resources provide a material basis for the development of medicine. In the early stage, the people of She accumulated a large number of folk unilateral and prescription tests through the exploration and attempt of the medicinal value of local animals and plants. For example, use mountain herbs to treat common diseases such as colds, fever, trauma, etc. In the process of fighting against natural disasters and diseases, the She people have gradually formed a unique theoretical system of medicine, paying attention to the balance and harmony between the human body and the nature, and treating diseases as the result of the imbalance between the human body and the natural environment. With the development of history, the She medicine culture continues to be inherited and enriched. The family elders impart medical knowledge to the younger generation, and some She doctors also organize and record their medical experience. In the exchange with other ethnic groups, it has also absorbed some foreign medical knowledge and further improved its own medical system. Its medical culture has always been rooted in the natural environment, taking natural products as the source, and plays an important role in ensuring the health of she people and ethnic reproduction.

19. Explore the participation of she people in social change in modern history and its influence on national consciousness.

In modern times, she people actively participated in the social reform. In the peasant rebellion such as the Taiping Heavenly Kingdom Movement, many She people devoted themselves to it and resisted the feudal rule and oppression together with other nationalities. This participation process enables she people to come into contact with a wider range of social thoughts and reform ideas, broaden their horizons, and enhance their national confidence and sense of unity. During the Revolution of 1911, some She intellectuals and progressives responded to the call of the revolution, propagating democratic and republican thought and promoting the ideological enlightenment of she areas. They realized the importance of national equality and national prosperity, and the national consciousness was gradually sublimated from the traditional family and tribal level to the national state level. During the Anti-Japanese War, she people are indispensable, actively participate in anti-japanese national salvation activities, such as organizing guerrillas, for the anti-Japanese army supplies and intelligence, etc., which further strengthens the minority national identity and patriotism, make she deeply realize their nation is an important member of the family of the Chinese nation, in peril have responsibility and obligation with other nationalities to defend national sovereignty and territorial integrity, thus greatly promote the minority national consciousness in the modern social change wave of awakening and development.

20. Analyze the association and interaction between she handicraft development and commercial trade from a historical perspective.

She handicrafts have a long history, such as textile, embroidery, silver jewelry making and bamboo weaving. In the early days, these handicrafts mainly met the internal living needs of the nation, such as making clothes, decorative supplies, production tools, etc.

With the rise of commercial trade between She people and surrounding ethnic groups, handicraft products have become important trade commodities. The exquisite textiles, gorgeous silver ornaments and exquisite bamboo weaving of the She people are very popular among other ethnic groups in the market. The demand of commercial trade promotes the continuous development and innovation of She handicrafts, with more exquisite craftsmanship and more exquisite design, so as to improve the competitiveness of products. For example, in order to cater to the preferences of the Han market, She embroidery integrates Han auspicious patterns into the pattern. At the same time, the economic income brought by commercial trade also provides financial support for the development of handicraft, buying better raw materials and tools, and cultivating more handicraft talents. This connection and interaction not only promotes the inheritance and development of She handicrafts, but also promotes the economic and cultural exchanges between She and surrounding nationalities, forming a commercial culture and handicraft industry system with She characteristics in the regional commercial network.

She dress category:

1. Deeply discuss the color system of she traditional clothing, including the cultural root, symbolic significance of color selection and the change of color application in different occasions.

The cultural roots and symbolic significance of color selection: The traditional costumes of She people mostly take black and blue as the background color, and the black and blue mainly come from the natural colors of their early textile fibers such as hemp and cotton, which also symbolize the industrious, simple, deep and introverted national character of she people. Red is an important decorative color in the costumes of She people, which is related to the ancestor worship and the concept of life reproduction of She people. Red is regarded as a symbol of auspiciousness, enthusiasm and vitality, and is mostly presented in the form of embroidery and ribbons, implying the yearning for a better life and respect for ancestors.

Color application changes in different occasions: in daily work, She costumes are mainly black and blue, and the style is simple and practical and convenient for activities. And in the festival celebration such as "March 3", womens clothing will use a large number of red and other bright colors such as red, the silver on the headdress is more gorgeous, the whole dress color collocation is more rich and gorgeous, to show the national happy atmosphere and the attention of the festival. On the wedding occasion, the brides dress color is the most bright, the red wedding dress is embroidered with exquisite patterns, symbolizing the festival and the beginning of a new life, the grooms dress is relatively solemn, mainly black and blue, with red decorative elements, reflecting the respect for the wedding ceremony and the responsibility for the family inheritance. In the sacrificial occasion, the color of the dress is relatively simple and elegant, mainly black and blue. The accessories will reduce the gorgeous decoration, reflecting the reverence and solemnity of the ancestors and gods.

2. Analyze the classification and design inspiration sources of She costume patterns, and explain how the patterns reflect the historical memory, myths and legends and life scenes of She minority.

Pattern classification: She costume patterns can be divided into natural patterns, such as flowers, birds, fish, insects, mountains and trees, geometric patterns, diamonds and circles; character patterns, mainly related to ancestral legends such as Panhu; character patterns, some ancient She symbols or deformation of Chinese characters.

Design inspiration source and embodiment: The inspiration of natural patterns comes from the natural environment where she people live, reflecting their love and awe for nature. For example, the flower pattern symbolizes beauty and vitality, while the bird pattern symbolizes freedom and agility. These patterns show the she peoples life interest in the mountains and rivers and their careful observation of nature. Geometric patterns often have abstract symbolic significance, which may be related to the religious belief or ancient totem worship of the She people. Their combination and arrangement contain the understanding and perception of the universe, heaven and earth, time and space. The character patterns take panhu and other ancestral images as the core, reflecting the memory of the origin of the She nation and the respect for the achievements of the ancestors, and inheriting the historical stories and cultural genes of the nation through the characters on the costumes. Text class design is a manifestation of minority culture inheritance and communication, some ancient symbols may be she early record or ideographic way, Chinese deformation patterns reflects the minority in the process of communication with han culture absorption and integration of the culture of Chinese characters, the use of the text pattern on clothing, both enriched the cultural connotation of clothing, and shows the diversity and inclusiveness of minority culture.

3. Explore the differences and connections in the design concept, functional embodiment and cultural connotation between She womens clothing and mens clothing. difference:

Design concept: She womens clothing pays attention to decoration and beauty, and the design is more complex and diverse. The neckline, cuffs and skirts of female tops are beautifully embroidered with rich patterns and colorful colors; skirts, decorated with exquisite ribbons, and gorgeous headdress, such as phoenix crown, with unique shape and numerous decorative elements, fully showing the softness and elegance of women. And the male dress design is relatively simple and generous, pay attention to practicality and convenience. Male jacket is opposite skirt short upper garment mostly, design is loose, easy working activity, color is given priority to with plain color, wait like black, blue, the complex embroidery of less large area, headdress is relatively simple, it is head scarf or cloth cap commonly, basically play warm and protective effect.

Function: The function of womens clothing, in addition to the daily wear of the warm body, is of great significance in social and cultural inheritance. Its gorgeous clothes show womens status and family wealth in festivals, weddings and other occasions, and are also an important carrier of inheriting national culture. They convey the history, beliefs and values of She nationality through the patterns, colors and other elements on the clothes. The main function of male clothing is to adapt to labor production, loose jacket

and simple style are convenient to stretch freely in field work, hunting and other activities, and also reflect the steady and simple men in social occasions.

Cultural connotation: The cultural connotation of womens clothing focuses more on the symbol of family, birth and national cultural inheritance. For example, the number of skirts is related to the 24 solar terms, implying the law of nature and the importance of agricultural production; the phoenix crown in the headdress symbolizes the important position of women in the family and the yearning for a better life. The connotation of male clothing more reflects the family responsibility, social role and national spirit. By wearing traditional clothes, men participate in family sacrifice, community affairs and other activities, showing their responsibility for family inheritance and national identity. The simple style of their clothes also reflects the tough and hard-working ethnic quality of She men.

Contact: Both are based on traditional colors such as black and blue, reflecting the she minoritys adherence to national traditional colors. In terms of pattern design, some basic patterns, such as Panhu image and some natural elements, are reflected in the men and womens clothes, but they are different in the form and position, which reflects the common inheritance of she ethnic culture in the men and womens clothes. In terms of cultural functions, men and womens costumes are the external expression forms of She ethnic culture. On important occasions such as ethnic festivals, weddings and sacrifices, men and women wear their own traditional costumes to participate together, showing the ethnic style and cultural characteristics of She culture, and jointly promoting the inheritance and dissemination of She culture.

4. Discuss the traditional selection and regional characteristics of she costume making materials, as well as the influence and challenge of modern materials application on traditional clothing.

Traditional selection and regional characteristics: She nationality traditional clothing production materials are more local materials. In mountainous areas, hemp and cotton are the main textile raw materials, hemp fiber is tough and durable, suitable for daily labor clothing; cotton fiber soft and comfortable, often used to make underwear or some decorative clothing parts. Bamboo is also used in She costumes, such as bamboo weaving is used to make hats, belts and other accessories, which reflects the rich bamboo resources in mountainous areas. In addition, some characteristic plant dyes from She areas are used for dyeing, such as dyeing blue with indigo. This natural dye is not only environmentally friendly, but also has a unique charm, which complements the traditional dress style of She areas and has distinctive regional characteristics.

The influence and challenges of the application of modern materials: modern materials such as chemical fiber and silk began to be used in the production of She clothing. Chemical fiber materials have the advantages of low price, easy processing, bright color and not easy to fade. They are used in some tourist souvenirs or She clothing in the mass consumption market. It expands the production scale and market coverage of She clothing, and enables more people to contact and understand the She clothing culture. However, it also brings about challenges. Chemical fiber materials lack the texture and cultural connotation of natural materials, and the excessive use may lead to the dilution

of the traditional characteristics of She clothing. Although the silk material has soft texture and good gloss, the price is high, which changes the original cost structure and consumption positioning of She clothing to a certain extent. It may make the traditional production process of She clothing deviate from the selection of materials, and it is necessary to find a balance between inheriting the traditional characteristics and adapting to the modern market demand.

5. Analyze the stitch characteristics, pattern implication and inheritance status of she costume embroidery technology from the perspective of cultural inheritance.

Characteristics of stitching: There are many kinds of stitching in She costume embroidery, such as flat needle embroidery, lock edge embroidery, seed embroidery and so on. Plain needle embroidery has smooth lines, often used for large area design, which can show the outline and texture of the pattern; lock edge embroidery is used for edge decoration to make the edge more firm and beautiful; seed embroidery has strong three-dimensional feeling, which makes the pattern more vivid. These needles cooperate with each other to form the unique craft style of She embroidery.

Pattern implied: embroidery pattern rich meaning. For example, peony pattern symbolizes wealth and prosperity; mandarin duck pattern means love and family harmony; butterfly pattern represents beauty and freedom. These patterns are not only decoration, but also the embodiment of she cultural values. They are passed on to future generations through costumes, so that the people can remember the national cultural traditions and life ideals.

Inheritance status: At present, the inheritance of She costume and embroidery technology is facing some challenges. On the one hand, the pace of modern life is accelerated, the young generation is not enthusiastic about learning traditional embroidery techniques, and there are fewer young people willing to engage in the embroidery industry, leading to the gradual aging of the inheritor group. On the other hand, the traditional embroidery craft is complicated, the learning cycle is long, and the economic benefit is relatively low, under the impact of the market economy, it is difficult to attract more people to invest their energy to inherit. However, some local governments and cultural institutions have been aware of this problem, and strive to promote the inheritance and development of she nationality embroidery costumes, according to the embroidery technology, and improve their popularity and influence in modern society.

6. Explore the types, plastic arts and production techniques of silver ornaments in She costumes, as well as the status and role of silver ornaments in she costume culture.

Type, plastic arts and production process: There are many kinds of silver ornaments in She costumes, including silver hairpin, silver hairpin and phoenix crown in headwear; silver collar in neck; silver medal in chest; silver bracelet and silver ring in hand. The plastic art is unique, and the phoenix crown is gorgeous, usually with phoenix as the theme, combining flowers, clouds and other elements, meaning auspicious and beautiful; the top of silver hairpin and silver hairpin is often carved with exquisite animal and plant patterns, such as plum blossom, butterfly, etc. Exquisite production technology, casting, forging, inlay, carving and other processes. The casting process is used to make the

basic shape of silver ornaments, while the forging is used to refine and shape the patterns, and inlaid gems or stained glass to add decorative features. The carving process makes the patterns more delicate and delicate, showing the superb skill level of the silversmith.

Status and role: Silver jewelry occupies an important position in the She costume culture. It is a symbol of the wealth and status of the She people. The more exquisite silver ornaments they wear, it often shows that the family has better economic conditions and has a high status in the family and community. At the same time, silver is an important carrier of minority culture heritage, its design and modelling contains rich national culture connotation, such as ancestor worship, nature worship elements, through silver wear and inheritance, the minority culture from generation to generation, in the national festival, wedding, sacrifice and other important occasions, silver is indispensable decoration elements, can enhance the beauty of beauty and ceremony, show the minority ethnic characteristics and cultural charm.

7. Analyze the style changes and dress matching principles of She costumes in different seasons, as well as the life wisdom and cultural concepts contained behind them.

Style change and dress collocation principle: in spring and autumn, the climate is relatively mild, the men and women's clothes are mainly single clothes, with cloth pants and headscarf; the collar and cuffs of female jackets are appropriate decoration, and the skirt is single or double layer, with ribbon decoration. Summer is hot, clothing material choice is more light and breathable, such as cotton or linen clothes, men may open the jacket or pull up the cuffs, female skirt will be slightly shorter, in order to facilitate heat dissipation. When winter is cold, the clothing will add the thermal layer. For example, wearing cotton-padded jacket and trousers, women will add thick petticoats to the skirt, and the hat or scarf on the head will be thickened. At the same time, fur and other thermal materials will be used as accessories.

Life wisdom and cultural concept behind it: This seasonally changing dress style and dress collocation reflect the life wisdom of the She people to adapt to the natural environment. Adjust clothing according to the climate characteristics of different seasons, can ensure the comfort of the body, and can facilitate a variety of production and living activities. In terms of cultural concept, the seasonal change of clothing also reflects the respect and adaptation to the natural laws. For example, the use of thermal materials such as fur in winter reflects the rational utilization of natural products, and is related with the She hunting culture; the light and simple use of summer clothing is compatible with the summer production activities such as farming and gathering, reflecting the interdependent relationship between She culture and production and life.

8. Explain the close relationship between She costume culture and the identity of the nationality, and illustrate the concrete embodiment of the identity identification of clothing.

She costume culture is an important external symbol of the ethnic identity. From the color, pattern, style and production process of clothing, they all contain a unique national cultural connotation. For example, the woven patterns and color combinations of the

ribbons on the costumes of She women have distinct characteristics of She women, and the ribbons may be slightly different in different families or regions. She women wear their family and region unique ribbons to show their family ownership and ethnic identity. The short skirt shirt and specific embroidery patterns are also one of the marks that distinguish she men from other ethnic men. In ethnic festivals, sacrificial activities and other occasions, she people dress in traditional costumes. Through the display of costumes, the sense of identity and sense of belonging within the nation is strengthened, so that the ethnic people can feel the cultural connection and national cohesion between each other. At the same time, in the communication with other ethnic groups, She clothing also enables the outside world to intuitively identify the identity of She, promotes the dissemination and exchange of ethnic culture, and further consolidates the status of She ethnic identity in the social and cultural level.

9. Discuss the innovative design ideas of She costumes in the context of modern fashion, and how to meet the modern aesthetic needs on the basis of retaining the traditional elements?

In terms of style innovation, the elements of loose opposite skirt and multi-layer skirt of she traditional costumes can be improved. For example, the skirt is designed into diagonal or asymmetric skirt to make the style more fashionable and modern; change the multi-layer skirt to single skirt, but retain the fold or decorative edge of the skirt, which reduces the weight of the dress without losing the traditional charm. In color innovation, in addition to the traditional black, blue, red, can appropriately add some soft tone or popular color as auxiliary color, such as light pink, light blue, etc., with the traditional color collocation, make the dress color more rich and harmonious, in line with the needs of modern aesthetic color diversity. Patterning innovation can be she traditional pattern to simplify or abstract processing, such as the complex flowers and birds pattern for the outline of the image, and then use modern printing or embroidery technology, with different combination way presented on clothing, or she patterns and modern fashion patterns such as geometric figures, letters, create a novel design style.

10. Analyze the interaction between the evolution of she costume style and the social, economic and cultural environment from the context of historical development.

In the early stage, She people focused on fishing, hunting and farming, the social structure was simple, the economy was relatively backward, and the dress style was simple and practical. The material is mostly hemp and cotton produced locally, the color comes from natural dye, and the style is easy to work, such as the loose short shirt of men and the simple dress of women, which is a direct reflection of the way of production and life at that time. As communication with the central plains culture, social stability during the tang and song dynasties, economic development, cultural prosperity, she clothing began to absorb some elements of the central plains clothing, color becomes rich, increased the decorative design, production process is more fine, reflects the economic after the pursuit of aesthetic and cultural connotation promotion, but also reflects the influence of cultural fusion on dress style. During the Yuan and Ming

dynasties, the process of political unified management and ethnic integration was accelerated, and the styles of She costumes were further standardized. For example, the design of collar and cuffs were influenced by the costumes of Han nationality, which was closely related to the political rule and ethnic exchanges at that time. Qing dynasty, commercial prosperity, she and the han and other ethnic trade frequently, clothing style on the basis of maintaining their own characteristics more delicate, exquisite embroidery, silver used, both embodies the minority culture heritage, also reflects the commercial economy of clothing culture, get more exquisite material through tradeMaterial and production technology, make the clothing become an important load to show the national culture and economic strength

11. Discuss the presentation mode and dissemination effect of She costume culture in the field of film, television, stage and other art.

In the field of film and television, she minority costumes often appear as an important element to show their national characteristics. For example, in some historical dramas or ethnic films, actors wear traditional costumes of She, and show the cultural style of She through the colors, patterns and styles of the costumes. In terms of costume modeling design, attention is paid to restoring the details of She costumes, such as womens phoenix crown, ribbon, mens double short shirt, etc., so that the audience can intuitively feel the unique charm of She costumes. In terms of stage art, the costumes of the She nationality song and dance performances play a role in making the finishing point. The dancers wear brightly colored and beautifully decorated She costumes, showing the agility and beauty of the costumes through dance movements on the stage. In some large-scale artistic performances or national culture display activities, she costume culture is presented in the form of theme show, combining traditional costumes with modern stage design, and creating a strong national atmosphere through lighting, music and other elements. Its transmission effect is remarkable, can attract the attention of a large number of audience, make more people understand she clothing culture, stimulate their interest in minority culture, and promote she clothing culture spread in a wider range of people, promote minority culture visibility and influence, but also as the minority clothing culture inheritance and innovation provides a new motivation and ideas.

12. Analyze the integration relationship between She costumes and She traditional etiquette culture, such as dress norms in weddings, sacrifice and other occasions.

On wedding occasions, she costumes strictly follow the traditional etiquette norms. The bride usually wears a red wedding dress, embroidered with exquisite patterns, and wears a phoenix crown, symbolizing happiness and dignity. The groom is dressed in a black or blue short shirt with red decoration to show solemnity and responsibility. These costumes are not only for beauty, but also reflect the role positioning and family expectations in the wedding ceremony. In the sacrificial activities, the clothes of the participants are more solemn and solemn. Generally, black and blue is the main color, reduce gorgeous decoration, women may take off some bright accessories, men are neatly dressed, wearing a scarf or cloth hat. This dress norm reflects the respect for the ancestors and the gods, and indicates the seriousness of the sacrifice. She traditional

etiquette culture can be visually presented directly through clothing, which becomes the external form of etiquette norms; the etiquette culture also gives She costume deeper cultural connotation, making it have specific symbolic significance and functions in different occasions, and maintains her ethnic culture tradition.

13. Explore the cultural display and tourist experience design of She costume culture in tourism development, as well as the positive and negative impact on the inheritance of costume culture.

In the development of tourism, many She minority communities display the She minority costume culture by establishing folk culture villages and holding ethnic costume exhibitions. Visitors can enjoy different styles and ages of She costumes, and understand their production techniques, patterns and meanings, etc. In terms of tourist experience design, set activities to experience the charm of She costumes and conduct a costume making experience course, where local craftsmen teach simple embroidery and weaving skills. The positive influence is that the tourism development provides a financial support and communication platform for the inheritance of She costume culture. The attention and participation of more tourists make the She costume culture more widely publicized, which is conducive to cultivating the young generations interest and sense of identity to the national costume culture, and promoting the inheritance and innovation of traditional crafts. However, there are also negative effects. Excessive commercialization may lead to the one-sided interpretation or distortion of She costume culture, and some tourist souvenirs are poorly made in pursuit of profit, which damages the image of She costume culture. The influx of a large number of tourists may make the traditional clothing production technology lose its original cultural connotation and quality due to meeting the market demand, so it is necessary to pay attention to the balance between cultural protection and commercial interests in the process of tourism development, so as to realize sustainable cultural inheritance and tourism development.

14. Explain the practical path and problems of She costume culture in school education and community inheritance.

In terms of school education, some schools in She communities have incorporated She costume culture into the school-based curriculum. Through class explanation, picture display, physical observation and other ways, the students are taught the history of She costumes, style characteristics, pattern implication, production technology and other knowledge. Organize students to visit the local She costume museum or handicraft workshop, so that students can experience the process of costume making personally, and cultivate their hands-on ability and love for national culture. In the process of community inheritance, the community regularly holds she costume culture festival, handicraft competitions and other activities to encourage residents to participate. In daily life, the family elders teach the costume making skills and cultural connotation to the younger generation, forming a model of combining family inheritance and community inheritance. The main problems are limited school education resources, lack of professional teachers and perfect teaching materials, and it is difficult to carry out clothing culture education systematically. In the community inheritance, the younger

generation is not highly interested in traditional costume culture, and is more inclined to modern pop culture, and has low enthusiasm to participate in inheritance activities. At the same time, with the acceleration of urbanization, the traditional life style of She communities has changed, and it is difficult to find some community activities related to the inheritance of clothing culture to be carried out continuously. It requires the government, schools, communities and families to work together to integrate resources and improve their youth. The cultural consciousness of the first generation is used to promote the effective transmission of She costume culture

15. Analyze the formal beauty rules of She costumes from the aesthetic perspective, including the aesthetic characteristics of modeling, proportion, symmetry and other aspects.

From the perspective of modeling, she costumes has a unique aesthetic feeling. The phoenix crown of womens clothing is gorgeous, with phoenix as the main body, combining flowers, clouds and other elements, with smooth lines and full of dynamic movement, showing a clever and noble beauty. The short shirt of male dress is simple and generous, and the use of straight line reflects the masculinity of men. In terms of proportion, she clothing pays attention to the overall harmony. For example, the length of a womans skirt is coordinated with the proportion of the jacket. Generally, the skirt is longer, which can show the elegant posture of the woman, while the length of the jacket is moderate, which will not be too long or too short to affect the overall effect. In terms of symmetrical beauty, many She dress patterns adopt symmetrical design, such as embroidery patterns on the neckline and cuffs. The left and right sides are completely symmetrical, giving people a balanced and stable aesthetic feeling. At the same time, she dress on the color collocation also follow certain aesthetic principles, such as black, blue as the background, with red bright colors as the ornament, primary and secondary, in contrast, enhance the visual impact and beauty, these form beauty law constitute the she dress unique aesthetic style, reflects the minority peoples pursuit of beauty and aesthetic concept.

16. Discuss the role and influence of She costume culture in cross-cultural communication, and how to enrich itself from other ethnic costume culture.

In the cross-cultural exchange, the She costume culture is the cultural name card of the she culture. It attracts the attention of other nationalities with its unique colors, patterns and styles, showing the national characteristics and cultural charm of the She nationality. For example, in international cultural exchange activities or domestic multi-ethnic cultural exhibitions, the display of She costumes can make people with different cultural backgrounds understand the history, belief and life style of She minority, and promote the dissemination and exchange of culture. She costume culture is also influenced by other ethnic costume culture and borrowed from it. In the communication with the Han nationality, I absorbed the embroidery stitch, pattern layout and color collocation concept of the Han nationality clothes to make my clothes more exquisite and exquisite. When communicating with the Miao nationality and other ethnic groups, we drew on the exquisite skills and unique shapes of her silver ornaments production

technology, and enriched the types and styles of the She nationality silver ornaments. Through this cross-cultural communication and reference, she clothing culture on the basis of maintaining their own characteristics of continuous innovation and development, improve its cultural connotation and artistic value, enhance the adaptability and competitiveness in the multicultural environment, further promote the minority clothing culture in the world national clothing culture of the forest unique status and influence.

17. Analyze the development status, market prospect and brand construction strategy of She minority clothing and culture industry.

At present, the she costume culture industry is in the initial development stage. Some areas have begun to pay attention to the development and utilization of She clothing, and some small clothing production workshops and sales shops have appeared, mainly producing and selling traditional She clothing, tourist souvenirs and some modern clothing products with She clothing elements. However, the industrial scale is small, the production technology is relatively backward, and the lack of standardized production process and quality control system. The market prospect is broad. With the increase of peoples interest in ethnic cultural tourism, the demand for clothing products with ethnic characteristics is also rising. The unique cultural charm of She clothing can attract many consumers, and both the domestic tourism market and the international cultural exchange market have great potential for development. In terms of brand building strategy, we should pay attention to excavating the connotation of She costume culture to create a representative brand image. For example, unique brand logo are characterized by traditional costume patterns or crafts. Strengthen product innovation, develop a variety of clothing products series, to meet the needs of different consumers. At the same time, the Internet platform and social media are used to carry out brand promotion, improve brand awareness, participate in cultural industry exhibitions and fashion weeks and other activities at home and abroad, display She clothing and cultural products, enhance brand influence, and through brand buildingTo promote the scale and standardized development of she clothing culture industry

18. Explain the internal connection and coordinated development mechanism between She costume culture and She folk handicraft inheritance system.

The She costume culture is closely linked to the folk handicraft inheritance system. Clothing production involves textile, embroidery, silver jewelry making, bamboo weaving and other folk handicrafts. Textile technology provides basic materials for clothing, and the quality of its inheritance directly affects the material quality and style characteristics of clothing. Embroidery craft is the core of she costume decoration. Exquisite embroidery patterns make the costume more cultural connotation and artistic value. The inheritance and innovation of embroidery artists are of vital importance to the development of costume culture. The production process of silver jewelry adds a sense of magnificence and status symbol to the costumes, and the skills inherited by the silversmiths ensure the exquisite presentation of silver jewelry in the costumes. Bamboo weaving techniques are used in clothing accessories such as hats, belts and other aspects, and its unique weaving techniques have enriched the types and styles of clothing. In terms of

collaborative development mechanism, the inheritance of various handicrafts is combined with the inheritance of costume culture through family inheritance and mentoring inheritance. When the family elder teaches the younger generation, they cover a variety of handicraft knowledge, and the craftsmen should innovate and develop in the process of inheritance skills. At the same time, the government and social organizations promote the coordinated development of costume culture and folk handicraft inheritance system through the establishment of cultural inheritance bases and holding handicraft training and competitions, so as to provide for the inheritance of both Platform and resource support to ensure the continuous development of She costume culture and folk handicrafts

19. Explore the new ways of protection and dissemination of she costume culture in the digital age, such as the application of virtual reality, network platform and other technologies.

In the digital age, virtual reality (VR) technology can be used to create a virtual display space of She costume culture. Users can enjoy the She costume exhibition through VR equipment, and see the details of the costumes, such as embroidery patterns, silver decoration techniques, etc., as if they are in the She culture museum. The network platform provides a convenient way for the she costume culture to spread it. Establish special She clothing culture websites and social media accounts, regularly publish pictures, videos and articles of She clothing, and introduce the history, production technology, cultural connotation and other knowledge of clothing, so as to attract the attention of the majority of netizens. The live broadcast platform is used to hold live broadcast of she costume production process, invite craftsmen to show embroidery, weaving and other skills, answer the audiences questions, and enhance the interactivity. Sell She clothing and related cultural products through the e-commerce platform to expand the market scope. In addition, digital animation technology can also be used to make animated short films or games with the theme of She costume culture, to spread the She costume culture to the younger generation in a vivid and interesting form, improve its popularity and influence in the digital era, and promote the protection and inheritance of She costume culture.

20. Analyze the role and expression of She costume culture in shaping gender role and family culture inheritance from the perspective of sociology.

In terms of gender role shaping, She costume culture has obvious embodiment. The gorgeous decoration and complex crafts of womens costumes, such as phoenix crowns and exquisite embroidered skirts, emphasize the feminine softness, delicacy and the role of family guardians. By making and inheriting costume techniques, such as embroidery and weaving ribbons, women closely connect their patience and skillful skills with their family culture, and assume the important responsibility of inheriting national culture in the family. The simplicity and practicality of mens clothing reflects the masculinity, diligence and the role of family pillar. Men wear short shirts that are easy to work to participate in production activities, providing economic support for the family. At the same time, in family sacrifice and other activities, men wear traditional clothes to show the inheritance

and majesty of the family. In the family culture inheritance, she clothing is an important carrier. The family elders teach the costume making skills and cultural connotation to the younger generation, and make the She costume culture to continue through the family. The dress standard in the family also reflects the family ethics and cultural traditions, such as wearing specific clothes on specific festivals or occasions, which strengthens the cohesion and cultural identity of the family, and promotes the stable inheritance of She family culture between generations.

She customs:

1. Discuss in detail the cultural connotation and ritual process of the she nationality "March 3 rd" festival, as well as the practice of inheritance and innovation in the contemporary society.

Cultural connotation: "March 3 rd" is an important festival for she people to commemorate their ancestors, pray for happiness and celebrate spring ploughing. It originates from the ancestor worship of the She people and their gratitude to nature. On this day, the She people remembered the achievements of their ancestors Panhu and three princesses through various ceremonies and activities, and thanked the life and ethnic inheritance given by the ancestors. Meanwhile, "March 3" is the spring ploughing season, which also means praying for the gods for good weather and good harvest, reflecting the close combination of the traditional farming culture and religious belief, which is an important embodiment of the She national spirit and cultural identity.

Ceremony process: On the day of the festival, a she minority village will hold a grand sacrificial ceremony. First, put offerings in ancestral halls or specific sacrificial places, such as wine, meat, fruit, tea, etc., to offer sacrifices to ancestors. Then the elders or priests of the clan presided over the sacrificial ceremony, read the sacrifice, tell the stories of the ancestors, and pray for the blessing of the ancestors. After the sacrifice, a variety of folk custom activities will be carried out. Men and women cover historical legends, love stories, labor and life, etc. She traditional dance, such as dragon dance, bell knife dance, dancers show national vitality and joy. In addition, She traditional sports activities such as mountaineering competition. All nationalities and young participate in the happy atmosphere of the festival.

Inheritance and innovation practice of contemporary society: In terms of inheritance, many governments and non-governmental organizations in she minority communities actively attach importance to the protection of "March 3 rd" festival culture. Through the establishment of a cultural inheritance base, the young generation of inheritors are trained, and the festival sacrificial ceremonies, singing and dancing skills, traditional customs and other contents are systematically arranged and taught. In school education, the relevant knowledge of "March 3 rd" of She people is also incorporated into the local curriculum or school-based curriculum, so that more She teenagers can understand and inherit the festival culture of their own nation. In terms of innovation practice, some regions combine the "March 3 rd" with the tourism industry. A large-scale "March 3 rd" cultural tourism festival will be held to attract tourists from all over the world to enjoy and experience. In the form of activities, in addition to traditional folk activities, modern

cultural displays such as She costume show and cultural creative products exhibition, etc. In the means of communication, the Internet and new media platforms for online live broadcast and short video publicity, expand the popularity and influence of "March 3 rd" festival, which not only promotes the inheritance and development of She culture, but also drives the development of local economy, and realizes the deep integration of culture and tourism.

2. Analyze the contradiction and coordination between the traditional ceremony of marriage proposal, engagement and marriage and the trend of modern simplification.

Traditional rituals:

Proposal: the man usually invites the matchmaker to the womans home for marriage. The matchmaker should bring gifts such as tea, cakes, etc., to express the mans sincerity and willingness to propose to the womans parents. If the womans parents are interested, they will discuss relevant matters with the matchmaker, including the understanding of the mans family situation, character and other aspects. This process focuses on the communication and negotiation between the family.

Engagement: The engagement ceremony is relatively grand, the man should prepare a rich bride price, including gold and silver jewelry, clothes, wine and meat delivered to the womans home. The womans home will return gifts, generally a few handmade items such as embroidery, weaving. At the same time, the two sides will determine the date and location of the wedding and other important matters, and invite friends and friends to witness the engagement ceremony, which strengthens the family marriage relationship and social contract.

Marry: On the day of marriage, the groom should go to the womans home to greet him, accompanied by the best man. In the womans home to go through a series of tests, such as songs, riddles, to show the grooms wisdom and sincerity. When the bride goes out, she should be carried out by her brothers or elders, meaning not to give up her family. Back to the mans home, to hold a worship ceremony, the new couple to heaven and earth, ancestors, parents salute, and then enter the bridal chamber. During the whole wedding process, there are many etiquette norms and traditional customs, such as singing wedding songs, sprinkling sugar, etc., full of a strong national cultural atmosphere.

Trend and contradiction of modern simplification: The pace of life in modern society is accelerating, and some traditional ceremonies of She nationality weddings are gradually simplified. For example, the promotion process may not be so complicated, through modern communication such as telephone and Internet; the types and quantity of betrothal gifts will be reduced and pay more attention to practical needs; some test links in the wedding process may be omitted, and the time of the wedding ceremony may be greatly shortened. This simplified trend and contradiction between traditional ceremony, traditional ceremony bearing she profound cultural connotation, family concept and social ethics, simplify may lead to the loss of some cultural connotation, weaken the family between the wedding in the process of communication and emotional fusion, may also make the younger generation of this national wedding culture understanding and inheritance is not comprehensive.

Coordination mode: In order to coordinate contradictions, it can be moderately simplified on the basis of retaining the core cultural elements of traditional rituals. For example, despite the modern communication, arrange a formal meeting ceremony, with the characteristic gifts to inherit the cultural significance of marriage, some symbolic traditional items, such as manual embroidery, can be retained to reduce unnecessary material burden; in the wedding link, keep the worship and other important ceremony, some test links into interesting cultural display activities, let the couple and relatives and friends together, which simplifies the process and inherits the culture. At the same time, through cultural education, folk custom exhibition and other ways, strengthen the publicity and education of the younger generation on the connotation of She wedding culture, so that they can understand the importance of traditional ceremonies, so as to better inherit and innovate she wedding customs in modern life.

3. Discuss the view of life and death and the connotation of religious belief contained in the funeral, funeral and burial customs.

Stop coffin: She nationality has the custom of stopping coffin for burial, and the stop time usually varies from three to seven days. This custom reflects the She minority's reverence for life and death and her respect for the soul. They believe that the soul will not leave immediately after death, the coffin is the last time between the soul and the family, the family to accompany, but also to provide time for distant relatives to offer condolences. During the suspension period, there will be some simple sacrificial ceremonies, such as placing offerings in front of the coffin and lighting incense, which reflects the ancestor worship in the She religious belief. It is believed that the souls of the ancestors will still pay attention to the situation of the family after death, and the soul can be comforted through sacrifice, and pray for the ancestors to bless the safety of the family.

Funeral: During the funeral, the She people have the custom of singing funeral songs. The content of funeral songs is mostly the review of the life of the dead, the memory of the dead and the thinking of the cycle of life and death. This reflects the generosity and detachment in the view of life and death of the She people. She believes that death is another beginning of life. She expresses her thoughts and blessings for the dead through the funeral song, and hopes that the dead can rest in peace in another world. Funeral procession route and ceremony also have exquisite, usually along the specific route to the cemetery, by the male in the coffin, the symbol of the family of the dead farewell and bear of life and death, also embodies the concept in the funeral, minority family members to participate in farewell the dead, maintain the family unity and inheritance.

Interment: She tradition is mainly earth burial, choosing cemeteries pay attention to feng shui, believing that good cemeteries can bless future generations. This reflects the continuation of the family and the welfare of the descendants in the view of life and death. To bury the dead in a suitable place is not only a respect for the dead, but also a hope to bring good luck to the family with the power of nature. In the process of burial, there will be some sacrificial ceremony, such as burial goods placed in the grave, including the dead living favorite items or some symbolic items such as rice, meaning the dead in another world can also live rich, but also expressed the love of the living and the dead,

embodies the soul of minority religion not destroyed concept and respect for the ancestors.

4. Explain the expression forms and cultural functions of she ancestor worship customs at the family, family and community levels.

Family level: In the family, the portraits or tablets of ancestors are generally offered on the main wall of the main room. At important moments, such as wine, wine, meat, fruit, cakes, etc., to carry out sacrificial activities. Family members will pray to their ancestors, praying for family safety, health, happiness and smooth career. At the same time, the family elders will tell the stories, achievements and family history of the ancestors to the younger generation in daily life, inherit the family culture and values, so that the family members can establish respect for the ancestors and a sense of belonging to the family from an early age.

Family level: the family will build the ancestral temple, which is an important place for the families to carry out collective ancestor worship activities. In the ancestral hall, sacrificial ceremonies are held regularly, usually presided over by the family elders or patriarch, with the participation of the whole family members. The sacrificial ceremony is solemn and solemn, including reciting offerings, offering offerings, and bowing rites. Through these rituals, the blood connection and family identity among family members are strengthened, and the cohesion of the family is enhanced. The compilation and revision of the family genealogy is also an important embodiment of ancestor worship. The genealogy records the family lineage inheritance and ancestral deeds in detail, which is an important record of the family history and an important basis for the family members to trace their roots and inherit the family culture.

Community level: In the She community, the custom of ancestor worship promotes the harmony and stability and cultural inheritance of the community. Some communities jointly hold large-scale ancestor worship activities, where members of different families gather together to remember their ancestors. This activity not only strengthens the connection and communication between the families, but also enhances the unity and mutual assistance among the community residents. The moral norms and cultural traditions contained in ancestor worship, such as respecting the old and loving the young, diligence and kindness, unity and mutual assistance, have become the values followed by the community, played a positive role in guiding the social order and cultural construction of the community, and promoted the inheritance and development of She community culture.

5. Analyze the relationship between the She nature worship customs and the local ecological environment, as well as the value transformation under the modern environmental protection concept.

Interrelationship with ecological environment: She people live in mountainous areas and other areas with rich natural environment, and their nature worship customs are closely linked with the surrounding natural environment. They worship natural elements such as mountains, rivers, trees and animals, believing that these natural objects have gods and are closely related to human life. For example, the worship of mountains and

forests makes she people pay attention to the protection of forest resources. They will not cut down trees at will, only moderate cutting when necessary, and will actively plant trees to maintain the ecological balance of mountains and forests. The worship of rivers makes them cherish water resources, do not dump garbage in the rivers, pollute the water source, and ensure the clean and ecological function of the rivers. The worship of animals enables She people to have certain taboos in hunting activities, not excessively kill some animals, and maintain the stability of animal populations. In the long-term historical development process, this nature worship custom has effectively protected the local ecological environment and formed a mode of harmonious coexistence between man and nature.

Value transformation under the modern environmental protection concept: Under the modern environmental protection concept, the nature worship custom of She people has important value transformation significance. Its traditional concept of respecting nature and protecting nature is consistent with the modern concept of environmental protection, which can provide useful reference for modern society. She settlements can be the natural worship culture combined with modern ecological tourism, development with natural worship culture experience as the theme of tourism projects, such as visiting the ancient worship natural god place, understand the relationship with ecological protection, etc., both spread the minority culture, and promote the development of local ecological tourism. At the same time, the ecological wisdom contained in the nature worship customs of the She people can be extended to a wider range of social groups through cultural publicity and education, so as to raise peoples awareness of environmental protection, promote the whole society to form a good fashion of respecting and protecting nature, and contribute to the construction of modern ecological civilization.

6. Discuss the special dishes, cooking methods and the social and economic factors behind the she traditional food culture.

Special dishes and cooking methods: She has many special dishes, such as She family black rice, glutinous rice soaked with black rice leaves steamed, black and shiny, soft and waxy taste, with a unique fragrance; Kan reed, with Kan grass leaves wrapped glutinous rice, beans and other ingredients, and then with palm leaves tied after cooked, slender shape, delicious taste. There is also green yeast wine, with local glutinous rice, herbs and other raw materials, through a unique brewing process made, the wine is yellow-green, with health care effect. In the cooking method, the common cooking, steaming, stew, roast and so on. Cooking and steaming are often used to make staple food and some dishes, such as the cooking of rice, vegetables and meat, which can retain the original flavor of ingredients. Stewed food is suitable for stewed meat and some root vegetables to make the ingredients more flavor and release nutrients better. The baking method is often used to make some special snacks, such as baked sweet potatoes, roasted corn, making the food golden and crispy, and sweet and delicious inside.

Social and economic factors behind food culture: In society, she food culture is closely related to family inheritance and social activities. Many traditional dishes are

made from generation to generation within the family, and women play an important role in the family diet production. They continue the family's food culture by inheriting their cooking skills. In social occasions, such as festivals, weddings, sacrifices and other activities, a specific diet is essential. For example, in the "March 3rd" festival, black rice is an important festival food, which is shared by the whole family. This is not only to satisfy the appetite, but also to enhance the national cohesion and cultural identity through food. In terms of economic factors, the natural products in the She minority living area determine the choice of dietary raw materials. Rich glutinous rice, all kinds of wild vegetables, mountain goods and domestic livestock in mountainous areas have become the main source of food ingredients. Due to the relatively backward economy in the past, the processing and cooking methods of food ingredients are relatively simple, focusing on the use of local resources to produce delicious and nutritious food at the least cost. With the development of economy, although some new food ingredients and cooking technologies are gradually introduced, the traditional food culture is still deeply rooted. In the development of modern tourism and cultural industry, the traditional diet has become an important cultural tourism resource, further promoting the local economy.

7. Explore the internal connection between architectural layout, interior decoration, family ethics and family order in the living customs of She people.

Architectural layout, family ethics and family order: The traditional buildings of She nationality are mostly courtyard layout, generally centered on the main room and symmetrical distribution of the left and right wing rooms. The hall is an important place for family activities and sacrifice to ancestors, reflecting the core position of the family and respect for the ancestors. In terms of family ethics, the elders live in the main room and the younger generation lives in the wing room. This layout defines the status and role of family members and reflects the orderly family ethics concept of the long and the young. In terms of family order, in some larger family settlement buildings, the living areas of different branch families are also divided to a certain extent. Each branch family is built around the family ancestral hall, and the family settlement community is formed around the ancestral temple, reflecting the hierarchical order and blood relationship network within the family. For example, the branch family where the elders or the patriarch of the family lives near the ancestral temple, symbolizing its leading position in the family. The other branch families are distributed in order according to blood kinship, which strengthens the cohesion and management order of the family through the architectural layout.

Interior decoration, family ethics and family order: Interior decoration also reflects family ethics and family order. On the main wall of the hall, portraits or tablets of ancestors are offered, and some family honors or family instructions will be hung around them to remind family members to follow the values and moral norms of the family and inherit the family culture. On the decoration of the room, the decoration of the elder room is relatively solemn and traditional, while the junior room may have some decorative elements that reflect the young people, but also will follow the overall cultural atmosphere of the whole family. For example, in the traditional She family, there may be

some embroidery works in the womens room, which is not only the embodiment of female craftsmanship, but also reflects the role of women in the inheritance of family culture. Through the differences and commonalities of interior decoration, the norms of family ethics and the inheritance of family culture are displayed.

8. Explain the inheritance system, teaching content and core significance of the inheritance of She culture.

Inheritance system: The custom of "teacher learning" is generally inherited within the family or between teachers and apprentices. Usually, the elders or masters who are highly respected and proficient in she minority culture and skills serve the family, and the younger generation or people who are interested in learning she minority culture serve as learners. The inheritance process is more solemn, with specific ceremonies and procedures. In some important festivals or family gatherings, teacher worship ceremonies are held, where learners salute to the masters to express their respect and determination for the inheritance of knowledge and skills. Later, in daily life and specific learning time, the master imparts to the learners she cultural knowledge, historical legends, religious rituals, singing and dancing skills, handicrafts and other contents through oral teaching and practical demonstration.

Teaching content: The teaching content covers many aspects of She culture. It includes the historical and cultural knowledge of the origin legend and family genealogy of She nationality, which enables the learners to understand the roots of the nation and family inheritance, the process, meaning and hosting methods of religious ceremonies, such as the ritual specification of sacrificial ancestors, the singing techniques, dance movements and dragon head dance of She nationality, and the operation methods and pattern design knowledge such as textile, embroidery and silver jewelry making. Through these rich teaching contents, the essence of She culture is fully inherited.

The core significance to the inheritance of She culture: the custom of "teaching teachers" has an extremely important core significance to the inheritance of She culture. It is an important carrier and way of She culture inheritance, which ensures the continuation of she culture between generations. Through this face-to-face and hand-in-hand inheritance method, the connotation and spirit of She culture can be deeply taught, so that learners can not only master the surface form of cultural skills, but also understand the cultural significance and values behind them. This custom to strengthen the national cultural identity, learners in the process of learning, deep understanding of she unique culture, enhance the sense of pride and sense of belonging, to more actively participate in the cultural heritage, promote the minority culture in the family, community and the whole nation within the scope of inheritance and development, maintain the uniqueness of minority culture and vitality.

9. Analyze the specific manifestations and cultural constraints of she taboo customs in daily life, productive labor, social etiquette, etc.

Performance and function in daily life: In daily life, she nationality has many taboos. For example, avoid eating dog meat, think dogs are friends of human beings and have a special status in the She legend, eating dog meat is regarded as a violation of national

tradition and moral norms; avoid whistling in the house, the legend of whistling will attract ghosts, which reflects the She fear of the supernatural power and the maintenance of family peace; avoid the first day of the lunar calendar and beat children, these two days are regarded as special days, reflects the She respect for traditional customs and gods, but also help to create a harmonious family atmosphere. These taboo customs play a role in regulating peoples behavior and maintaining family harmony and cultural traditions in daily life, making she people always follow the national cultural norms in their daily life and form good living habits and moral customs.

Performance and function of productive labor: In productive labor, she nationality also has some taboos. For example, during the sowing season, avoid saying unlucky words and worry about affecting the harvest of crops, which reflects the importance she attaches to agricultural production and the awe of the power of nature. During hunting, there are some taboos about prey, such as not killing some animals regarded as spiritual at will, which helps to maintain ecological balance, and also reflects the nature worship concept of She people. These taboo customs encourage she people to follow certain norms in production and labor, treat labor production with a positive attitude, and respect the laws of nature, ensure the sustainability of agricultural production and hunting activities, and also inherit the production culture and ecological culture of She people.

Performance and function in social etiquette: in social etiquette, she taboo customs are forbidden to hand tea to the guests, which reflects the respect and courtesy to the guests; in the communication with elders, there are strict etiquette norms, such as the elders, respectful, which strengthens the orderly family concept and social ethics. These taboo customs regulate peoples communication behavior in the social etiquette, promote the harmony of interpersonal relations, show the cultural accomplishment and national image of She, and contribute to the stability of the social order of She and the inheritance of cultural tradition.

10. Discuss the expression and mechanism of She customs in the process of cultural adaptation and change from the perspective of cultural anthropology.

Performance: In terms of cultural adaptation, she ethnic customs have gradually absorbed and integrated some foreign cultural elements in the process of communication with other ethnic groups. For example, in costume customs, some features and production techniques of Han costumes are absorbed to make them more exquisite and varied, the architectural layout and decoration techniques of Han nationality are used to improve living conditions. In the process of cultural change, the form and connotation of some traditional customs have changed. For example, on the "March 3 rd" festival, on the basis of the traditional sacrifice, song and other activities, the modern elements of cultural display and tourism activities are added, and its functions have expanded from the simple national internal memorial and entertainment to cultural communication and tourism economic drive. In the wedding customs, with the development of modern society, some complicated ceremonies gradually simplified, at the same time into the modern marriage registration and other legal procedures, so that the traditional wedding and modern social system to adapt.

Mechanism: Cultural communication and exchange is an important mechanism for the adaptation and change of She customs. The long-term trade, population migration and cultural exchange between She nationality and Han nationality and other surrounding ethnic groups make different cultures contact and influence each other. Economic development is also a key factor. With the improvement of the economic level in the She minority areas, peoples life style has changed, and their cultural demand and consumption have also changed, prompting the adjustment of customs. For example, the rise of modern tourism industry makes She customs become tourism resources. In order to meet the needs of tourists and the requirements of the market, the customs are innovated and changed in form and content. In addition, policy guidance and social education have also played a driving role. The governments policy support for the protection and development of ethnic culture encourages She people to inherit and innovate ethnic customs; school education and social culture publicity make She people have a deeper understanding of this national culture, and promote the adaptability of customs in modern society, so as to maintain the vitality and sustainability of national culture.

11. Explore the cultural display and tourist experience design of She customs in tourism development, as well as the influence on the inheritance of customs.

Cultural display and tourist experience design: In the tourism development, she customs are displayed in various ways. For example, the establishment of folk culture village, focusing on the display of she nationality architecture, clothing, food, singing and dancing and other customs and culture. Visitors can visit the traditional She architecture to understand their layout and decoration characteristics; watch the She costume production and display, appreciate its exquisite craft and unique style; taste the She characteristic food, feel its unique taste; enjoy the She song and dance performance, experience its cheerful rhythm and rich cultural connotation. In terms of tourist experience design, interactive links are set up. For example, tourists can participate in the traditional handicraft production of She, such as learning embroidery and weaving skills, personally making souvenirs with She characteristics; participate in the singing and dancing with local residents; and also participate in the traditional festivals of She, such as "March 3" festival, to experience the fun of sacrifice and singing activities. Through these cultural display and tourist experience design, tourists can have a deep understanding of she customs and culture.

Impact on custom inheritance: The positive influence lies in that tourism development provides a new platform and financial support for the inheritance of She customs. The attention and participation of more tourists make the She customs and culture more widely publicized and improve its popularity and influence. At the same time, it also stimulates the local residents pride and protection consciousness of their national customs, and promotes the inheritance and development of the customs in the local area. For example, some traditional handicrafts that may have been forgotten have been paid attention to and inherited in tourism development, and young people are more willing to learn and inherit the singing and dancing skills of their own nation. However, there are also negative effects. Excessive commercialization may lead to the distortion or

alienation of she customs and culture. In order to meet the needs of tourists, some custom performances may lose their original cultural connotation and gravitas, and become simple entertainment programs. The influx of tourists may also be a source of impact on local traditional customs and life, changing the natural environment and social foundation of customs inheritance. Therefore, in the process of tourism development, it is necessary to pay attention to the protection of she customs and cultural connotation, so as to ensure the mutual promotion and coordinated development of tourism development and customs inheritance.

12. Analyze the unique functions and development status of she songs in social entertainment, emotional expression, and cultural inheritance.

Unique features:

Social entertainment: She folk songs are an important way of social entertainment for she people. In festivals, weddings, parties and other occasions, people enhance the communication and interaction between each other through singing. There are various forms of duet, including male and female duet, group duet, etc. The lyrics are rich in content, covering life anecdotes, historical legends, labor experience and other aspects. This singing activity not only enriches peoples spiritual and cultural life, but also provides a communication platform for people from different families and villages, and promotes the harmonious development of social communication and interpersonal relations.

Emotional expression: folk songs are also an important carrier of the emotional expression of she people. In the process of love, the young men and women express their love through the song, and convey the inner feelings and ideas through the song, euphemism and deep feeling. In the face of the joys and sorrows in life, people will also use folk songs to express feelings, such as in the labor tired, sing a folk song to relieve the body and mind; in the face of difficulties or sadness, through the inner pain, seek comfort and strength.

Cultural inheritance: She songs and customs play an irreplaceable role in cultural inheritance. Folk songs contain rich sources of historical and cultural knowledge of She people, such as ethnic origin, ancestral deeds, traditional customs and so on. Through the singing activities handed down from generation to generation, these cultural contents can be inherited and continued, so that the young generation can understand the cultural foundation of the nation in the song, and enhance the sense of national identity and belonging. At the same time, the tunes and singing styles of folk songs are also an important part of She music culture, which maintain the uniqueness and diversity of She music in the process of inheritance.

Development status: At present, the She minority song customs have been inherited and developed to a certain extent. In the She ethnic community, the custom of singing still retains in some traditional festivals and cultural activities, and many folk singers are committed to inheriting and carrying forward the She ethnic folk song culture. The government and cultural departments have also taken some measures to protect and promote She song customs, such as holding folk song competitions, cultural festivals and other activities, encouraging young people to participate in learning and singing She folk songs, and cultivating a group of young folk song lovers and inheritors. However,

with the impact of modern culture and the change of social life style, the she minority song customs are also facing some challenges. The love and pursuit of pop music has reduced their attention to traditional folk songs and their enthusiasm to learn folk songs is not high. In addition, the diversification of modern entertainment modes also makes the position of traditional singing activities in social entertainment gradually replaced. The inheritance and development of She singing customs need to further explore new ways and new modes to adapt to modern society.

13. Discuss the performance forms and cultural symbolic significance of she dance customs in sacrifices, celebrations, festivals and other occasions.

Sacrificial occasions: In the ceremony of sacrifice to ancestors or gods, she nationality dances such as dragon head dance and bell knife dance have solemn and solemn performance styles. In the dragon head dance, the dancers hold the dragon head props to simulate the movements of the dragon, such as circling, taking off, etc. The movements are slow and powerful, symbolizing the respect and prayer for the ancestors and gods. The bell knife dance takes the bell knife in the hands of the dancers as the main prop. Through rhythmic dancing, it emits a clear bell. It is said that it can drive away evil spirits and disasters and bless the smooth progress of the sacrificial activities. It also expresses the She peoples reverence for the ancestors and gods and their belief in the supernatural power.

Celebration occasions: In weddings, housewarming and other celebrations, she dance is more cheerful and lively, full of festive atmosphere. For example, some dances will incorporate local folklore or legend elements to bless the newlyweds or express good expectations for a new life through the interpretation of the dance movements and plots. The dancers are large, the rhythm is lively, often accompanied by laughter. The whole dance scene is lively, symbolizing happiness, reunion and the prosperity of the family, and becomes an indispensable part of the celebration, enhancing the happy atmosphere and cultural connotation of the celebration.

Festival occasions: For important national festivals such as "March 3 rd", She dance is an important form of displaying national culture. There are various forms of dance and a large number of participants, such as group dance, pas de deux and so on. The group dance is like the bamboo pole dance. The dancers jump and shuttle between the opening and closing of the rhythmic bamboo poles, showing the unity, cooperation and vitality of the She people. These festival dance is not only to celebrate the festival, but also the concentrated expression of minority national spirit and cultural characteristics, a symbol of the minority people love of national culture, inheritance and national identity, through the dance performance, the minority history, beliefs, values and other cultural connotation to every participant and the audience, promote the spread of national culture and communication.

14. Discuss the handicraft customs and the inheritance and cultural innovation of the customs of She nationality, such as weaving and paper cutting.

Inheritance of skills: She weaving, paper cutting and other handicraft production skills are mainly continued through family inheritance and mentoring inheritance. Within

the family, older women usually teach weaving skills to younger women, from basic weaving techniques such as weaving bamboo baskets and straw MATS, to complex pattern design and color collocation, which are taught hand in hand in daily life. For example, the unique patterns and color combinations of the She ethnic ribbons weaving contain the cultural information of the family and the nation, which can be preserved through family inheritance. In terms of mentoring inheritance, some masters who are good at handicrafts will recruit apprentices to teach paper-cutting and other skills. The apprentices followed the master to learn the composition and cutting skills of paper-cutting, and gradually mastered this skill from simple flower and bird patterns to complex characters and story patterns. At the same time, the local government and cultural institutions are also actively promoting the inheritance of handicraft skills, holding training courses and establishing training centers, to provide more people with opportunities to learn and cultivate a group of young handicraft inheritors, so that these traditional skills can continue to be passed on in modern society.

Cultural innovation: On the basis of inheritance, she nationality handicraft production customs are also constantly undergoing cultural innovation. On weaving technology, in addition to the traditional bamboo weaving, straw products, began to try to use modern materials such as color thread, plastic rope, combined with traditional materials, create novel weaving works, and in the design into modern elements, such as modern geometry, popular cartoon image, etc., make woven works more in line with the modern aesthetic demand, broaden the market. Paper-cut art, on the basis of the traditional paper-cut style and cultural connotation, the innovation of paper-cut forms, such as paper-cut and modern decorative art, made into paper-cut frame, paper-cut lamps and other household decorations, or develop paper-cut art derivatives, such as paper-cut bookmarks, paper-cut phone case, increased the practicability of paper-cut art, and make it more widely used in modern life, enhance the cultural value of minority handicraft custom and market competitiveness.

15. Explain the cohesion function and cultural integration function of She customs in community construction and ethnic unity.

Cohesion: She customs play a powerful role in community construction. For example, in the She villages, the common festival customs such as "March 3 rd", the whole community residents will participate in the preparation and celebration of the festival. We prepared sacrificial supplies, organized singing and dancing performances, and held traditional sports activities together. In this process, we enhanced the interaction and cooperation between the residents, and promoted the harmony of the neighborhood relations. Family customs, such as ancestral temple sacrifice, genealogy revision and other activities, make the family members closely united together, forming the family cohesion, and the unity of many families constitutes the overall cohesion of the community. In terms of ethnic unity, she customs understand and respect each other with other ethnic groups through cultural exchange activities. When other ethnic groups participate in the She ethnic festival celebration or cultural display activities, they can feel the unique charm of the She ethnic culture and enhance the friendship and unity among ethnic groups. For example, in some multi-ethnic areas, she dances and handicraft

exhibitions and other activities have attracted the participation and appreciation of other ethnic groups, promoted the cultural exchange and integration among various ethnic groups, and enhanced the ethnic cohesion of the whole region.

Cultural integration function: She ethnic customs are also of great significance in cultural integration. It integrates the history and culture, religious beliefs and values of the She people together to form a complete cultural system. For example, the ancestor worship custom of She people runs through all levels of family, family and community. Through sacrificial ceremony, family inheritance, the national historical memory, family ethics and social norms are integrated, so that the She people can inherit and practice the cultural values of the nation in the process of following the customs. In the cultural exchange with other nationalities, she customs will also absorb the excellent cultural elements of other nationalities and carry out cultural integration and innovation. For example, the embroidery techniques and pattern design concepts of the Han nationality are absorbed in costume customs, and the architectural styles and decoration techniques of other ethnic groups are borrowed in architectural customs, so that she culture is constantly enriched and developed on the basis of maintaining its own characteristics, and promotes the diversified integration and harmonious coexistence of regional cultures.

16. Analyze the integration mode of She customs in the modern education system and the effect of cultural inheritance education.

Integration method: In the modern education system, She customs are mainly integrated through curriculum setting, campus cultural activities and practical teaching. In terms of curriculum setting, some schools in the She minority communities have incorporated the She minority customs and culture into the local curriculum or school-based curriculum. For example, the history and culture courses of She people introduce the traditional festivals, clothing customs, food customs, handicrafts and other contents of She people in detail, so that students can systematically understand the customs and culture of their own nation. In the campus cultural activities, the school will hold the She culture festival, folk custom exhibition and other activities to display the She costumes, handicrafts, singing and dancing performances, etc., to create a strong She cultural atmosphere, so that students can personally feel and experience the charm of She customs in the activities. In terms of practical teaching, students are organized to conduct field visits and practical activities in she minority villages, folk culture villages and other places. Students can participate in the handicraft production process of She, such as learning ribbon weaving and paper cutting, watch the dance performance and try to learn some simple dance movements; participate in the traditional festival activities of She, such as "March 3" sacrificial ceremony and singing activities, so as to deepen the understanding and understanding of the customs and culture of She, through practice.

Effect of cultural inheritance education: this integration method has achieved a certain effect of cultural inheritance education. Through course study, campus activities and practical experience, students have a deeper understanding of She customs and culture, and enhance their national pride and cultural identity. Many students have developed a strong interest in She handicraft production in the learning process, and

actively learn and inherit these traditional skills. Some schools have also cultivated a group of students with certain She cultural accomplishment and handicraft skills, who can become a new force for the inheritance of She culture. However, there are some problems. Due to the limited faculty, some teachers do not have a deep understanding of She customs and culture, and may not be able to impart relevant knowledge comprehensively and accurately in the teaching process. At the same time, the modern education entrance pressure factors may also lead to she custom culture education in school education of time and energy into relatively insufficient, affect the effect of cultural heritage education, need to further strengthen teacher training, optimize the curriculum and teaching arrangement, in order to improve the she custom culture in inheritance education in the modern education system quality.

17. Discuss the resource transformation and product development strategies of She minority customs in the cultural and creative industries.

Resource transformation: She ethnic customs contain rich cultural and creative industry resources. For example, the traditional clothing patterns, colors and styles of She people can be transformed into fashion design elements and applied to the design and development of clothing, accessories, household goods and other products. The embroidery patterns in She costumes are extracted and designed into prints and embroidery decoration of modern costumes, or made into necklaces, bracelets, earrings and other ornaments with national characteristics, as well as household ornaments such as pillows and curtains, so that the cultural elements of traditional costumes can be innovatively applied in modern products. She traditional handicrafts such as weaving, paper cutting and other skills can also be transformed into cultural and creative product resources. Weaving skills can be made into a variety of exquisite handicrafts, such as bamboo vases, straw storage boxes, etc.; paper cutting art can be made into modern paper cutting art paintings, paper cutting greeting cards, paper cutting stationery and other products, combining traditional handicraft and modern life needs, to achieve effective transformation of resources.

Product development strategy: In terms of product development, a variety of strategies can be adopted. The first is a serialized development strategy, developing a series of related products with the theme of a certain custom and cultural element of she nationality. For example, with the "March 3 rd" festival of the She people, a series of products, including festival commemorative clothing, special food gift boxes, handmade souvenirs, cultural books, etc., are developed to meet the needs of different consumers and form a brand effect. The second is the personalized customization strategy. According to the personalized needs of consumers, she customs and cultural elements are integrated into the customized products. For example, the wedding costumes and home decoration products with She minority characteristics are customized for consumers to improve the added value of the products. Third, cooperative development strategy. Cultural and creative enterprises cooperate with She craftsmen and cultural inheritors to jointly develop products. Craftsmen provide traditional skills and cultural creativity, and enterprises are responsible for product design optimization, production and processing, marketing and other links, so as to realize complementary advantages,

improve product quality and market competitiveness, and promote the innovative development of She customs and culture in the cultural and creative industry.

18. Discuss the communication characteristics, communication channels and communication effect improvement strategies of She customs in the new media era.

Communication characteristics: In the era of new media, the dissemination of She customs is fast, extensive and highly interactive. New media platforms such as Weibo, WeChat and TikTok can quickly spread information about She customs, break through the limitations of time and space, and enable more people to understand she customs. For example, after a wonderful video of She song and dance performance is released on TikTok, it can get a large number of likes, comments and forwarding in a short time, and its spread scope far exceeds the traditional media. At the same time, the interactivity of new media enables the audience to interact with the communicators in real time. The audience can leave a message below the video and share their feelings and experiences. The communicators can also timely adjust the content and way of communication according to the audience feedback, which enhances the effect of communication.

Communication channels: New media provides diversified communication channels for She customs. Social media platforms are one of the main communication channels. By creating official accounts, they regularly publish pictures, videos, articles and other contents of She customs, such as introducing she traditional festival customs, handicraft production process, special food, etc. Video sharing platforms, such as TikTok and B stations, focus on the dissemination of short videos and long videos to attract audiences with vivid video content. In addition, cultural tourism websites and APPs can also be used as communication channels to introduce tourism resources and folk culture in She minority communities and attract tourists to experience them. There are also online live broadcast platforms, which can conduct live broadcast activities of She customs, such as live wedding and live production of traditional handicrafts, etc., so that the audience can feel the charm of She customs.

Communication effect improvement strategy: In order to improve the communication effect, a variety of strategies can be adopted. One is the content innovation strategy, the production of creative and attractive communication content. For example, she customs are combined with modern pop culture elements to make humorous short videos, animations or comics to attract the attention of young audiences. Second, precision marketing strategy, according to the user characteristics of different new media platforms and audience needs, targeted release of communication content. For example, publish content combining She customs and fashion design for young fashion groups on Weibo, and publish interesting short videos on TikTok for public users. Third, fan interaction strategies, actively interact with fans, reply to comments and private messages, hold online activities, such as She customs knowledge questions and answers, photography competitions, etc., to increase the engagement and participation of fans, expand the influence of communication, and make she customs more effectively spread in the new media era.

19. Analyze the association and mutual promotion between she customs and she

traditional sports activities.

Connection: She customs are closely linked with traditional sports activities. Many traditional sports activities originate from the production and living customs and religious sacrifice customs of the She people. For example, mountaineering competition is related to the living environment and hunting customs of the She people living in mountainous areas. Mountaineering skills are very important in hunting and daily work, and later gradually evolved into a competitive and recreational sports activity. For example, the activity of sharing the stone originated from the She people. It was originally held to pray for the blessing of the gods in a specific ritual venue. As time goes by, its entertainment and fitness functions gradually became prominent and became a traditional sports activity. In the festival customs, the traditional sports activities are a more important part. For example, in the "March 3 rd" festival, a variety of sports activities will be held, people celebrate the festival at the same time, through sports activities to show the strength and skills of the body, inherit the national culture.

Mutual promotion relationship: the two promote each other and develop together. Traditional sports activities enrich the connotation and form of she customs. The addition of sports activities to festivals, sacrifices and other custom activities makes these activities more colorful, attract more people to participate, and enhance the vitality and attraction of the custom activities. For example, adding some traditional sports events, such as archery competitions, can increase the festive atmosphere and fun of the wedding. At the same time, she customs also provide a platform and power for the inheritance and development of traditional sports activities. Due to custom activities held regularly, traditional sports activities in specific times and occasions show and inheritance, stimulated the enthusiasm of people to participate in sports activities, cultivate the fans of traditional sports activities and inheritance, make the minority traditional sports activities in the soil of national culture constantly inheritance and innovation, maintain a strong vitality.

20. Discuss the stability and variation characteristics of she customs from the perspective of folklore theory.

Stability characteristics: She ethnic customs have a certain stability. Its core cultural connotation and basic form have been retained in the long-term historical development process. or example, ancestral temple worship and genealogy revision in ancestor worship customs have always been an important way for she families and communities to inherit national culture and gather family strength, and their basic forms and cultural significance have not been fundamentally changed. Traditional festivals, such as "March 3 rd", keep the commemoration of the ancestors, gratitude to nature and the cultural theme of praying for happiness remain stable. This stability comes from the she peoples deep feelings and identity to the national culture. As an important carrier of the national culture, the customs carry the historical memory, values and life style of the nation, and can be steadily passed down from generation to generation through the family and community.

Variability characteristics: At the same time, she customs also have variability. In different historical periods and under the social circumstances, the customs will change

somewhat. In the process of cultural exchange with other ethnic groups, she customs absorb the cultural elements of other ethnic groups, which changes in form and connotation. For example, in the costume customs, influenced by the costume culture of the Han nationality, there are innovations and changes in the style and embroidery technology. In modern society, with the development of economy, scientific and technological progress and the change of life style, she customs are also adapting to the new environment. For example, traditional handicraft production has been updated in materials and tools, and the forms and participation methods of some custom activities have become more modern, such as the use of new media for the dissemination and promotion of custom culture.

Affected factors: there are many factors affecting the stability and variability of she customs. Cultural exchange is an important factor, and the extensive communication with other nationalities promotes the variation of customs, making them absorb new elements and adapt to the new environment. The level of social and economic development also plays a key role. Economic development provides the material basis and new demand for the innovation of customs, promoting the change in their form and content; while the relatively stable economic structure and lifestyle help the customs to maintain its stability. In addition, policy orientation, education popularization and the development of modern media also have an influence on She customs. The governments policy support for the protection and development of national culture helps to stabilize the inheritance of customs and encourage innovation and adaptation to modern society. The education makes she people have a deeper understanding and reflection of the national culture and promote the reasonable change of customs; the modern media accelerates the cultural exchange and dissemination, and broaden the channels and speed of custom variation, creating the characteristics of stability and variation of she customs.